

Middle East University

Faculty of Education

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT
AND CHILDREN'S ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN PRESCHOOL

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the

Requirements for the Degree

Master of Arts in Education

by

Mireille Jean Feghaly

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THESIS ABSTRACT

Master of Arts in Educational Leadership

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Title: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT
AND CHILDREN'S ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN PRESCHOOL

Researcher: Mireille Feghaly

Advisor: Shawna Vyhmeister, PhD

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The purpose of this study is to find out if there is a relationship between Lebanese, immigrant and refugee parental involvement, and their children's academic achievement in preschool.

Parents' role is to be the first teachers who should be present to support and to educate their young children. But often, they are not completing their job which could affect their children's academic achievement in different ways. Through this study, I used the quantitative method for statistical analysis to determine the result and to answer my research questions numerically. This aims to determine the relationship between two independent variables. I used ANOVA to find if there are differences in parental involvement (capable, responsible, and willing) in Lebanese, immigrant, and refugee children. I also used qualitative analysis to determine the type and amount of parental involvement. A sample of sixty families is representative of a certain population in Lebanon filled out specific questionnaires. The results showed the

presence of capable, responsible and willing parents who want to make a difference in their children's academic skills. Differences in attitudes toward parental involvement and in academic achievement were found by nationality, however these differences could not be modeled statistically using multiple regression.

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APPROVAL BY THE COMMITTEE:

Advisor: Shawna Vyhmeister, PhD

Date Completed

Reader: Rula Yazigy, PhD

Faculty Dean: John Issa, PhD

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Many children in the developing world don't develop to their full potential because of a lack of early opportunities for learning. As many as 200 million children in developing countries could learn so much more if their growth were not stunted by the lack of opportunities for learning early in their lives. Stages of cognitive development are based on linguistic, rational and understanding characteristics typically observed in children from economically advantaged countries considered as low-income and middle-income countries, as well as the cost of not investing in early child development.

Years ago, children's cognitive development was measured through intelligence quotient (IQ) tests, however, few valid and reliable tests of early cognitive development have been normed even in developed countries (Cherry, 2016). Thompson (n.d.) found that lower circuits in the brain must be constructed before complex circuits, and advanced skills must be founded on basic skills. But when children start kindergarten without being ready for it, there is surely something wrong that happened before.

One of the first concerns that comes to the teacher's mind is the effect of the students' parents or their preschool on their achievement. Before starting kindergarten, many children have spent between three and five consecutive years with their parents. Fathers and mothers think sometimes that their children are growing in a healthy way, once they are eating well, sleeping well and lacking of health issues. But

it seems that there is more to follow the baby's development than logging height and weight. There are a numerous of other early childhood milestones to consider. Through following a healthy development, every child should acquire different tasks by a certain age that could be classified as gross motor skills, fine motor skills, language skills, cognitive skills and social interaction skills.

During their first year of life, babies should have the ability to babble, move objects, crawl, and imitate people. After twelve months, they can walk independently and speak at least fifteen words. Between two and three years old, children can run, jump and enjoy playing independently. After the age of three, children can get along people outside the family, get dressed and count to fifteen and sometimes more (MayoClinic, 2014). Simple but fundamental skills, called *milestones*, are acquired by the toddlers till 5 years old (Baby Center, 2016 & Schissel, 2017). This development helps them to grow well and attain the next stage where they are full of desire to explore new things, new people, and themselves.

Milestone requires the children capability to realize tasks independently by a certain age. Milestones can include physical, cognitive, social, emotional, and linguistic skills such as walking, crawling, sharing with others, expressing emotions, recognizing familiar sounds, and speaking. In this case, a question comes to our mind: why are developmental milestones important? In her article entitled "What are developmental milestones?" Cherry (2017) found that the developmental milestones can be considered as a checklist that represents the average child can do around a particular age with a significant difference between children. And while looking at the different developmental milestones, parents, pediatricians, and educators can notice better the presence of any possible developmental problems. The milestone stage ends

at the end of five years old when children achieve most of the developmental signs before they turn six years old (WebMD, 2017).

Most parents want to be great parents but then again, they cannot achieve this goal. As the first teachers of a child, they probably are his/her first life inspiration. He/she will get his/her attitude, opinions, aims, and viewpoint from them and will build his/her life on what he/she learns from them. Studies show that “what a child learns in the early years is known to have a lasting impression, which is why good parenting is an absolute necessity” (Anamika, 2016, para. 2).

As human beings, parents cannot be perfect in all aspects. On purpose or by accident, they may abandon their children physically or emotionally, exposing them to physical violence or verbal abuse, complaining to other about them, do not support them or provide them their needs, and much more. All these affect the child development and classify the parental style as corrupted one.

When children start kindergarten, two clear symbols summarize all their previous life before this stage: their language skills and their behavior (Telehealth, 2016). Some children do not have the ability to communicate or to cooperate, control their impulses, have acquired motor skills, cognitive and intellectual development. They could have trouble in listening, obeying, following directions, separating from their parents, participating in groups, etc. It is well known that some children need more time to solidify and master skills, but this does not mean that in this case the parents should act as passive observers. They have to set the right foundation for learning and growing for the rest of their offspring’s lives. “Many children are still learning to control their behavior as they enter kindergarten and may need educational support to develop that critical skill, indicates one of the most conclusive studies to date of early childhood self-regulation” (Science Daily, 2016, para. 1).

According to the U.S. Department of Education (2015), six out of ten children are not ready to start kindergarten. This is from a very developed country—imagine what it must be like in less developed places. Students may suffer for the rest of their lives because of this slow start. This is the situation in general in the world, and in Lebanon too, whether among the Lebanese, immigrants, or refugee children who are growing up.

Writing about early childhood development, The United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF, n.d.), which aims to provide a fair chance in life to every child everywhere, declares that “children are the foundation of sustainable development. The early years of life are crucial, not only for individual health and physical development, but also for cognitive and social-emotional development” (para. 1). All these sources agree on the importance of this period that plays a fundamental role in each individual life.

Emotional, social and physical developments are the most important areas of a well-balanced growth in early childhood. Studies have shown that children’s development of the social and cognitive skills needed for future success in school may be best supported by a parenting style known as capable, responsive, and willing child raising process (Landry, 2014).

Capable Parents

Capable parents are those who have the competence and the ability to make a difference in their children’s life. They can use their knowledge, their proficiency, and their skills to push their children development forward. They can find time to spend it in teaching their young children to read together, play together, discover together and explore the world together (Sanders & Morawska, 2014). These parents are capable to show positive attitude toward their early children development.

Responsible Parents

Responsible parents are those who have duty to complete a target and which has a consequent penalty for failure. They are responsible to support their children to improve their academic skills (Kruk, 2008). Their role in this case is the sustenance and cooperation with the preschool program and to work in parallel for the best of their young children development. These parents are responsible for helping their offspring developing their cognitive, emotional and physical skills.

Willing Parents

Willing parents are those who are eager to accompany their children development process step by step. They want to do that and they desire to do it perfectly. This kind of parent could not be able to complete his/her target or maybe he/she is not responsible to do so, but his/her wish still exists. If the life circumstances or the daily problematic stop them, it does not mean that they are not willing to do that (Waldman, 2011). Their desire is to support their offspring and to present them the best, even if they could not do it, or they do it in an unprofessional way.

Qualified Parents

Becoming this kind of parent could be the most important job an individual will ever have. An early childhood parent requires the readiness to wear many hats. Qualified mothers and fathers are similar to guides who lead their children to new paths, walk beside them daily, support them always, protect their steps, and take wise decisions to help their reach their educational goal (Families for children, 2013). The role of parents starts from the first day of the mother's pregnancy and never ends. But in some cases, busy parents think that their role stops once their child goes to school. For them, it is the teacher's role to raise the child in an appropriate way. This

is because they are not willing to continue their role, or simply, because they are not enjoying the fact of being parents. These kinds of parents miss the privilege to be partners in learning. They do not support their children development neither facilitate their learning. Parents play a vital role in developing the knowledgeable and social development of children during their formative years. That is why it is crucial for them to be capable, responsible and willing.

When parents show care for their offspring in different areas, children do well in school and in life (see for example Paul, 2012; The Center for Parenting Education, 2017). But sadly, there is a lot of incomplete information, especially when we are talking about Lebanese parents and their role in affecting their children's academic achievement. Furthermore, we know almost nothing about immigrant and refugee parents' roles in Lebanon in this area too. Do parents in Lebanon get involved in their children's development in all areas? Do they feel responsible for helping their children grow and learn? Or do they lean heavily on the schools and consider their own role as unimportant? Do students do better when their parents are involved in their learning?

Lebanon is a small country of nearly four million citizens. However, regardless of its small size, it has been for years at the center of Middle Eastern conflicts, because of its borders with Syria (BBC News, 2016). Through the years, Lebanon has witnessed a series of waves of migration. Around three million foreign people live and work within its borders today (An-Nahar, 2013). Those people are raising their offspring with Lebanese citizens and they are also sending them to Lebanese schools. For their part, Lebanese citizens are worried that the arrival of these refugees may cause an existential crisis in their country where they already lack stability. All the daily political and economic challenges are upsetting their lives in all

areas, and entering their homes without permission (e. g. Mercy Corps, 2013). This is causing a lot of stress on them that many times hurts their relationships with their young children and affects their early years of development.

In addition to the refugees, the Lebanese population is also sharing its land with a huge number of other foreign people. In June 2016, the total number of foreign workers in Lebanon, not including the Syrians and the Palestinian citizens, was calculated at 270, 000 (An-Nahar, 2013). No doubt, these people have children who need shelter and places to stay during the day, so their parents can go to work as handymen, domestic workers or any other humble job they might find. Many of these migrant workers have come recently, seeking work. “Due to war at home, most of the group travelled to Beirut in the last year. But regular work has proved difficult to find” (Armstrong, 2016, para 2). Residency rules in Lebanon put Syrians at risk. One study found that “only two out of the 40 refugees interviewed said they had been able to renew their residencies” (Human Rights Watch, 2016, para 2). As for the Syrian crisis, as many as “1,170,000 Syrians are registered with UNHCR as refugees today” (Gebara, 2015, para. 1). Around 400,000 Syrian students attend Lebanese schools today (Jesri, 2015, para. 2). After a long journey filled with attacks, threats, risks and hunger, families, and children specifically, reach their new home in Lebanon in a terrible situation: physically and mentally exhausted.

When Lebanese, immigrant and refugee parents and children are living this very difficult situation, how can they support each other? As an educator and a preschool director who works in a non-governmental organization (NGO), I am facing daily a lot of challenging cases. Parents from different nationalities bring me their children and they expect the preschool to transform these little individuals into socially well-adapted geniuses, or at least educated citizens.

The problem in this case is that a large number of parents have ignored their primary role in the development process or have failed to notice that development starts from home. A large population does not comprehend that academic achievement is the result of fruitful parental involvement, and sadly, they do not recognize that they need to take into consideration a lot of other concerns that could be demographic, social, or familial, that affect this whole process. Cooperative problem-solving necessitates that parents and educators work together to determine and regulate proper resources and supports that facilitate the child's development.

Researchers at the University of Oxford found that “children whose parents participated in the Peers Early Education Partnership (a program geared towards supporting families of children ages 0-5) made significantly greater progress in their learning than children whose parents did not participate” (Hernandez, 2007, para. 3). On the other hand, a large number of parents are not able nor willing to play this role, neither do they feel it is their responsibility. That is why I want to study about the whole atmosphere and what possible support systems there may be for these Lebanese, immigrant and refugee students. How do parents understand their role in their children's lives? Can they make a difference and help the Lebanese, immigrant and refugee children through this difficult time? What are their beliefs and practices? How do they (or don't they) help? Does it make a difference? Do refugee parents feel less able or less willing or less responsible to help than other parents? Do some parents help more than other? Is there a relationship between parental involvement and children's academic achievement? These are some of the questions this study addresses.

Problem Statement

The parents should be the first teachers and main support for their toddlers in learning and development, but often they cannot or do not achieve this. This study examines parental involvement and its effect on preschool children's academic achievement for Lebanese, immigrants, and refugees in Lebanon.

Research Questions

1. How much are Lebanese, immigrant and refugee parents involved in their children's lives, and does this show in their academic achievement?
(Qualitative)
2. Are there differences in attitudes toward parental involvement based on demographic status? (ANOVA)
3. Are there differences in parental involvement (capable, responsible, and willing) in Lebanese, immigrant, and refugee children? (ANOVA)
4. Is there a correlation between parental involvement and children's academic achievement by nationality? (Correlation)

Delimitations and Limitations

This study delimits to the refugees, immigrants and Lebanese citizens found in one preschool (Grow Early Learning Center) in Bourj Hamoud, Beirut. While this is a very small sample, it represents sixty children from different backgrounds who lives in this busy area for many reasons. The nursery—which is planned to be a growth development center in the future—is under the cover of Resurrection Baptist church, Beirut, where migrant workers and refugees find a welcoming community of Christians, of which they can become a part.

The National Evangelical Church of Beirut – Philemon Project responsible- find out that migration is a extensive phenomenon in the Middle East. For migrant African and Asian workers, Lebanon seems to be economically prosperous, compared to the neighboring countries. By working in Lebanon they expect to send certain amount of money home to improve the lives of their family members. In several cases, however, migrant labors find that being in Lebanon is not as tranquil and simple as they supposed it would be. Abuse, low salaries, high living expenditures, lack of access to basic facilities, lack of liberty to move everywhere, becoming illegal: these are all pressures that migrant workers face daily and occasionally fall prey to.

The study covers a small sample in Lebanon, and not the whole population. It is drawn from sixty children in a preschool located in a busy area of Beirut. The sample represents the different nationalities and different socio-economic levels that exist in Beirut. The result could be generalized to some similar areas in the country, but not necessary on the whole to all Lebanese citizens.

Definition of Terms

Lebanese: In this study, Lebanese means the people who are originating from Lebanon. They are native members of the nation who belong to its government and are entitled to its protection.

Immigrants: In my study, immigrants are those who came to Lebanon to take up stable residence. They left their country in order to find better economic status and enhanced life style for them and for their families.

Refugees: In this study, refugees are the Syrian people who left their country because of the war that attacked their country and stole their history and their future.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The aim of this chapter is to discuss published information and research that covers the main subject of this study. It includes summaries and syntheses to recap the main information of the chosen resources, and to trace progression of the field.

This study covers the themes that concern the main role that parents play in the life of their young children. Parental involvement in early childhood development is the main focus of this study. I collect information from international thesis, studies, documents and articles that had studied this process in order to find out what they found and what they missed. My concern is to find out if the role of Lebanese, immigrant and refugee parents make a difference in their offspring development before the age of four, and to light up on their responsibility, willingness and ability to create this difference.

Early Childhood Development

When we talk about early childhood development, we typically refer to the growth during the infantile period, which lasts from birth to primary school entry. It is a kind of involvement designed to promote typical cognitive development that refers to aspects of brain development. These aspects occur with advances in psychological processes connected with awareness, retention, intellectual development, problem-solving, language-learning and brain development characteristics that occur with age and day after day. This early childhood stage has a reflective influence on the child's future. When children receive all they need in the way of love, nutrition, care and

safety, they develop their skills in the right way. This fundamental period of life is an opportunity that can make a difference in the future.

Neural Connections in Early Childhood Development

Studies have found that in the early years, seven hundred new neural connections form in the child's brain every second (Center for the Developing Child, 2009). These connections build what is called the "brain architecture" that provides the basis for all future knowledge, performance, and wellbeing. The future of an individual depends a lot on what happens to the individual during this stage. If the building process is weak, it damages the future of the child and vice versa. The foundation of this architecture is prenatal. First of all, simple neural connections form and lead to more composite skills. At that time, as many as one thousand new neural connections could be formed per second. After this stage, the connection decreases to permit the brain circuit become well-organized. Genes provide the formation of brain circuits that are reinforced by repeated use (Center for the Developing Child, 2009).

The main element of this process is the interaction between children and their parents. If it is absent or not present in the life of the young child, his/her tiny brain's architecture does not form as progress, which can create gaps in learning and behavior (Oates 2012). "The emotional and physical health, social skills, and cognitive-linguistic capacities that emerge in the early years are all important for success in school, the workplace, and in the larger community" (Center on the Developing Child at Harvard University, 2009, para. 4). When parents provide a child with positive practices during his/her early years, they build his/her brain architecture strongly. In this case, we can light up on the role of the parents and its importance in this process? Studies have found out that parents and caregivers play a vital role in their child's development (see for example Landry 2014; Ministerial Council for Education, 2010).

When the infant shows signs or motions and the adult reacts through touching him/her or by making eye contact, the child's brain makes neural connections that sustain and nourish the development of communication and social abilities. This technique is called by the scientists, the "serve and return technique," as it needs two partner to accomplish the goal. "When caregivers are sensitive and responsive to a young child's signals and needs, they provide an environment rich in serve and return experiences" (Center on the Developing Child, 2009, para. 1). From here, we can see the importance of parental involvement in early childhood development. Their presence is more than significant, and their absence is dramatically affecting the growth of their offspring (Share, 2013). The relationship between parent-child is essential for healthy brain architecture, and its absence submerges the brain development with damaging stress hormone (Moore, 2007).

Cognitive, Emotional, and Social Capacities in Early Childhood Development

The brain is a unified organ, and its various functions work together in a standard harmony. "Children develop cognitive skills rapidly in the first few years of life and build on them progressively throughout grade school" (Gilles, 2017, para. 1). When a child is involved in developing his/her skills, he/she processes sensory information and ultimately learns to estimate, examine, recollect, associate, understand and conclude. Some skills are genetically acquired but most of them are learned through experiences and training. In this case, we can light up on the importance of parental involvement in their early child's development process (Veraksa, 2011). From 2 to 5 years old, children developed specific skills to emphasis attention for long periods, identify encountered evidence, remember previous data, and rebuild it in the present. They can remember an event in the past and tell others

about it. In this period of time, their long-term memory begins to form. Piaget found out that “children in the Preoperational stage of development build on skills learned and mastered during the sensorimotor stage. During this stage, young children's play becomes increasingly imaginary and filled with fantasies” (Oswalt, 2017, para. 2). During playing time, children develop cognitively, and involve more characters, situations, games, sophisticated instructions and creativity. According to Piaget, playing isn't just fun; it is an important part of brain development. And here is a question to ask: what is the role of parental involvement in this case? Specific parenting performances and activities exploit children’s cognitive abilities. This cognitive stimulation has been defined as “parents’ didactic efforts to enrich their children’s cognitive and language development by engaging children in activities that promote learning and by offering language-rich environments to their children” (Lugo-Gil & Tamis-LeMonda, 2008, p. 1066).

Theories of cognitive development such as those of Vygotsky and Piaget (Child Psychology, 2017) have postulated that parental cognitive stimulation is a significant environmental factor of children’s cognitive abilities.

“Emotional development involves learning what feelings and emotions are, understanding how and why they happen, recognizing one’s own feelings and those of others, and developing effective ways of managing them” (Kids Matter, n.d., para. 1). Emotional learning commences at a very early stage, as young children start realizing a variety of feelings and reactions which progress as they grow. The early emotional development reproduces social experience. When they understand how to manage their feelings, young children remain peaceful and enjoy experiences. They are more likely to develop an optimistic sense of self and to be self-assured learners.

The child's emotional statuses become more complex day after day when he/she is exposed to diverse circumstances. Parents in this case play an imperative part in their child's emotional well-being. Their role consists on talking with their children about feelings and how to control them, and also, to set an example through replying to their child. Children gain knowledge, social and emotional skills through their relationships with families, caregivers, peers and early childhood staff (Zero to three, 2010). In this case, parental involvement occurs in helping their offspring managing their emotions by maintaining their feelings of love and safety. This target could be achieved in children's lives through the support of a responsive and caring caregiver. In early period of time, young people needs the help of their parents especially when they are feeling down or overcome to be able to manage their intense feelings. They could do it through their experiences with sincere, responsive adults (Summers, 2016). "Emotion reflections are when an adult recognizes the emotions a child may be experiencing and reflects this back to the child using words to name the emotion, matching voice tone and body language" (Kids Matter, 2016, para. 3).

Children, like other adult people, have ups and downs with daily circumstances. Refugees for example, who left their country and their places to travel to another country, face daily challenges and disappointments. These rough conditions put their life and their children development at risk and can be stressful for the whole family. In a similar case, adults are required to help their children shape resilience so they can enjoy the good times and manage with anxiety and frustration (see for example, Government of Canada activities and initiatives, 2016; Greenberg, 2012).

Social cognition could be sometimes known as emotional intelligence (Megan, 2010), and it has also a major role in children's social and emotional development (Fernández-Berrocal & Checa, 2016). We mentioned before its importance once it

concerns several psychological procedures that allow people to take advantage of being part of a social group. Now, we can explore its role in early childhood development.

“A close relationship between the child and the caregiver is the best way to nourish the child's growing brain” (Facts for life, n.d., para. 3). Children are social beings, and this capacity develops when they interact with adult and with other people or supportive. Many activities could occur in this area and could shape the child's behavior at the same time. The social ability is about identifying, understanding and responding to social circumstances in an appropriate way. It is known as protective factor for children's mental health and wellbeing (Kids Matter, n.d.).

One of the most significant developments in early childhood social cognition is the development of theory of mind. It takes place during the first five years of life and it covers the factors that impact children's growth, and the significances of their lives. It is about getting the child's ability to interact with other people and to understand that “others” exist. They could have another point of view, different taste, other look, etc. Children understand that the world does not look like them. “We use theory of mind to explain our own behaviour to others, by telling them what we think and want, and we interpret other people's talk and behaviour by considering their thoughts and wants” (Astington & Edward, 2010, para. 2). The development impacts their lives at home and school.

John B. Watson, Ivan Pavlov, and B. F. Skinner focused their studies on how environmental interaction influences behavior (Innovative learning, 2015). These theories deal with observable behaviors, and they do not give the internal feelings any importance. Albert Bandura worked within both cognitive and behavioral frameworks that embrace attention, memory and motivation. His theory of learning proposes that

individuals absorb within a social milieu, and that learning is simplified through notions and thoughts such as modeling, observational learning and imitation. He contends that children learn from observing others, which are processes involving attention, retention, reproduction and motivation (UNESCO, 2017). Social theories of child development have a tendency to emphasize the part that parents or caregivers play and its impact on the child's social development. From here, we can conclude that parents need to be the child's role model for a well-being growth.

In her study done in the United States, Christensen (2011) found that "play is an important aspect of supporting children's social interactions, which are central to their social development" (p. 12). She stressed that many children with and even without disabilities do not learn to cooperate properly without having another person who provides them this option and encourages them to interact. Additionally, a survey polled one thousand five African Americans shows that parents are not involved well in this area because of many daily issues related to income, housing, health care, relationships, race and education (G.White, 2014). The role of the parent is important for the development of their children. Their presence in their children's lives as mates, models, and teachers, etc. let their offspring grow well and develop their skills. Here is the role of capable, responsible and willing parents to achieve this part.

History of Parental Involvement

Education is not restricted to schools. Studies and research done in this area agree that parental involvement affects children's achievement (Center for Public Education, 2011; Gratz, 2006). In this section, I chose to look at what has been done in different countries because my study deals with two populations: Lebanese, Syrian refugees, and African immigrants. I look at the United States also because there is a

significant number of studies done there, at the time where African and European studies are quiet rare.

In Europe, parent/family involvement considerably contributes to enhanced student results related to learning and school success (Carter, 2000). He found that family contribution has reached a new level of acceptance as one of numerous influences that can support student's improvement. This is a sample of what is done in Europe. Parental involvement at home has important constructive consequences on children's achievement. Additionally, in the primary school age range the influence caused by diverse levels of parental involvement is much superior to differences associated with disparities in the quality of schools (Kernan, 2012).

In Africa, the case is different than in Europe. It seems that this continent lacks parental involvement which affects black student's quality of education. It has been primarily limited to financing schools (Lemmer, 2007). In Asia and in Japan for example, parental involvement is characteristically defined as the beginning of home-based behaviors such as monitoring child's behavior, attending school events, communicating with teachers (Holloway, 2008). In general, we can conclude that parents who are involved in their child's education make a joining between the home and school. At home, they are able to spread activities that their child practices in preschool or kindergarten. A responsible parent pick up where the school left off and have an instinctive sense for what his/her child needs to work on to increase his/her competency, skills, developmental area and well-being. Involved parents have a sense of responsibility to support the growth of their offspring. But what is the case in our Arab nation?

Parents as First Teachers

Parental involvement occurs as vigorous affect the children's educational outcomes. It could include monitoring indoor and outdoor children's activities. Studies show that a subtle, sincere, and approachable sort of parental engaging in performing and practicing activities with young children, strengths their social, emotional, cognitive and linguistic developments. The quality of the parent-child relationship is significant. Studies found that students, who received sensitive and sympathetic parenting from their mothers before the age of four, have a tendency to achieve better in school (Kim, 2008). These results are associated with long-term educational improvements.

The Graham Allen report on early intervention (2011) recognized parents as teachers as one of the indication which can consistently advance the lives of children and families. The role of parents in the life of their young children can extend the experiences that he/she has in the classroom to real-world activities that occur at home. Qualified parents know very well in which areas they need to work on to improve their offspring confidence, skills and ability. They know how to make strong effort to be as significant companion and partner in their child's education and his/her learning ability. Their attitudes toward education stimulate their children and show them how to be responsible of their own educational journey day after day. When they are young, children learned the acquisition of skills from their parents. At home, they learn to speak, to express, and to understand what is required from them. Language and other skills are smoothed by connections with their parents. This process may be supported or imposed.

Sadly, a significant number of parents do not consider themselves as teachers for many reasons. "Too small to fail" newsletter (2001) reminds us that babies learn

to recognize the voice of their mother and learn about their environment. And after birth, babies look to parents to help them make sense of the world around them, from new foods to new experiences. When these parents are neglected, non-willing, not able or irresponsible, the child process of good development fails (Hartwell-Walker, 2017; “Child neglect,” 2016).

Parents who are role models for learning, show their children how preschool or school can spread the learning they began together at home, and how exciting and meaningful this learning can be (Smith, 2015). They act as coaches and leaders. Through management, supervision and direction, parents help their children organize their time and support their needs to learn new things, explore new facts in and out of school. They notice their children to find out what they interest them to explore it together, side by side. It is well known that people could learn visually and other could learn by doing. People may not learn the same way others do (Kids’ Health, 2107). By supervising the child, they may be able to pique his/her interest and use his/her language to explain to teach him/her (Knauf, 2015).

Parental Attitudes Towards Reading and Speaking the Foreign Language

English language is measured as an international language; this is why it is vital to acquire it today. In Lebanon, this “global language” has an important role in education. In her article entitled “English assumes greater importance in Lebanese linguistic universe,” Hodeib (2007) found that “English is increasingly gaining status within what had been thought to be a francophone fortress” (para.7). She interviewed Mrs. Hala Shaftari, the head of the Anglophone books section at Library Antoine, who declared that the section was moved to cater to a growing number of English readers, and that English book sales are on the rise. This, in brief, is the case of

Lebanon today. People in Beirut communicate mostly in Arabic, but also they use many expressions in English and French at the same time. Therefore, the daily conversation is scattered with both French and English phrases, especially among adults. Day after day, the new generation is dropping its connection to the country's formal language: Arabic. Many citizens pride themselves on being fluent in English, and feel it is a dishonor and a shame to speak Arabic.

Based on this reality, I can conclude about the importance of speaking English nowadays. English (or French) as second language classes are extremely common in Lebanon, since it is not a national language of this country. It is a foreign language but the bases in schools where it shows as the foundations of a good communication. When a child masters this language in his/her early years, he/she shows readiness to enter the class with a minimum number of issues.

Older Sibling's Role in the Child's Development

In some other circumstances, older siblings may play the role of the parents. In a busy life, husband and wife have to find a job to cover the expenses of their family. In this case, grand parents could fill the role of the guardian to become the primary caregivers to young children who are in charge of their physical, emotional and cognitive development. Livingston (2013) found out that nearly 3 million grandparents in the United States assist as primary caregivers for their grandchildren. They develop old-style relationships with their grandchildren and have the additional duties that complement the parental role. In Asia, the case is more valuable. Asian childcare is affected by the cultural values and beliefs that influence parents, especially concerning family life and social relationships. Asians incline to have a big family with a large number of children (Detzner, 2010). Typically, up to three or four generations live together in the same building, or in the same neighborhood. Nuclear

families could have four to eight children, depending on socioeconomic status and ethnic group. Their culture demands from them a strong relationship between each other, which means that members must care for each other. The role of grandparents and older siblings in this case is to care for the young and adult children. “Family relations and functions are clearly and elaborately defined. Mutual two way obligations connect families, helping them with tasks such as parenting and creating strong bonds” (Detzner, 2010, para. 3). These grandparents provide an important way for young children to learn important skills from older adults, as well as family history.

Older siblings also play a very significant and vital part in young children’s lives by presenting supervision and management on humble activities or social customs. New research shows that the learning that takes place between younger and older siblings is impulsive and two-sided. It means that older siblings frequently offer coaching to younger siblings without being asked, but younger siblings often ask their older siblings how to do things, too.

Factors Affecting Early Childhood Development

There are several factors that can have a direct effect on a child’s development. Young children are so susceptible and they can be easily affected by any influence. The child could lack of stimulation, overdue motor skills, abridged hearing, unstable environment, exposure to diverse languages and high nervousness situations. Also, parental interactions with their offspring can have a mainly effect on their development. When they spend quality time interacting with them, they impact them positively. On the other hand, when they ignored or abandon them, they may delay their healthy development.

The environmental factors have their importance in this case, such as income and education that all mark a child's development. A safe environment offers a chance to explore, provide healthy nutrition, nonviolent shelter, suitable clothing, educational toys and access to resources and programs. A harmless community offers for the child the opportunities to explore and to develop well and vice versa.

Factors Affecting Student Academic Achievement

When talking about factors that affect students' achievement, main questions that concern the spent life of the young child come to the mind: Does the child have safe space to play and explore? Does he/she have suitable clothing for each weather? Is he/she eating healthy food on time? Does he/she have quality child care, when parents are away or working? Is his/her family suffering from financial stress or a high debt load? What level of education do family members have? All these questions and much more are vital to ask in this case to light up on the whole atmosphere where the early child breathes daily and spends each instant of his/her life.

Poverty

Once I chose my population from a poor and busy area, I found out that it is vital to talk about the effect of poverty on student academic achievement (Evans, 2004). When poverty overwhelms a family, young children are the most vulnerable. Their rights, their lives, their growth and their future will be all at risk. "A child born today in the developing world has a 4 out of 10 chance of living in extreme poverty" (UNICEF, 2001, para.1). Poverty threatens the children's presence through famine, deficiency of clean water, insufficient hygiene, etc. It is one of the fundamental causes of millions of deaths all around the world. This aspect let early children be undernourished, underweight, miss out education and face violated their rights. Also,

poverty effects the child's rights to psychological, emotional and spiritual development which are violated every day. It causes these young citizens to survive randomly without boundaries and without educational motive. "Poverty causes millions more to be sold into bondage to pay off family debts or abandoned to institutions because a family is without resources. And causes others to be left on doorsteps in urban slums or starved and neglected, hidden from view in city apartments" (UNICEF, 2001, para. 8).

Different influences impact school success, right from the beginning of child's life as well as preschool programs and early childhood period of time. Studies have shown that parents' attitudes, background, history and beliefs have a huge impact on children's development (Child Trends, 2012; Gorard & See, 2013; National Endowment for the Arts, 2015). They are performing in accord with information about appropriate parenting acquired through books, Web sites, external guidance, old experiences, opinions, and moods that are activated during parenting. All these stimuli influence their relation with their children. Their attitudes involve the amount of acceptance or refusal that exists in the parent-child connection, as well as the degree to which parents are tolerant or obstructive in the limits they set for their children. "Attitude is a psychological state that is expressed through agreement or disagreement with a certain situation or value" (Abu-Rabia & Yaari, 2012, p. 171). Parents demonstrate their appraisals of circumstances through their responses that could be cognitive, affective or behavioral and that show that attitude and behavior are well connected.

Family Structure and Children's Achievements

Succeeding research has verified that family background is strongly correlated with student' performance in school and has showed that the family structure has also

a big impact on the child's development. A constant family is one of the highest positive influences on early childhood development rates. In their paper entitled "Family structure and children's achievements," Ermisch and Francescon (2000) found out that "experience of life in a single parent family is usually associated with disadvantageous outcomes for young adults; most of the unfavorable outcomes are linked to an early family disruption, when the child was aged 0-5" (p. 249).

Usually, a family support that involves two married individuals provides care, constancy, loyalty and stability for their biological offspring. However, when one parent is absent for any reason, his/her absenteeism affects the whole educational process. The child who has been born to an unmarried parent or whose parents were married and then separated or divorced conflated with experiencing family instability. We can easily confirm that the structure of the family into which a child is born and grows, presents equally benefits and difficulties that consequently mark cognitive, socio-emotional and even physical health results. Changes in family structure are complemented by variations in financial and parental incomes; this state places pressure on families and harms the child outcomes. This instability produces a sense of anxiety concerning home rules (Amato, 2000; Cavanagh & Huston, 2006; Kelly & Emery, 2003; Osborne & McLanahan, 2007).

"Academic Success Begins at Home." This is how Kim (2008) entitled her study in which she found out how children succeed in school. Kim found out a strong relationship exists between parental influences and children's educational results, from school readiness to college completion. She stressed out on two main points which are the family structure and parents' involvement in their children's schoolwork. According to her, to improve the child educational outcomes, parents have to start consolidating their marriage first and afford a stable and constant family

formation. This kind of atmosphere creates a safe environment that let the child feels secure and protected. Once the whole milieu is safe, the young individual becomes ready to grow well. According to Kim (2008), “Studies show that children raised in intact families, tend to fare better on a number of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral outcomes than children living in other family forms” (p. 3). She lights up on the importance of the family structure that marks children’s school products, from preschool to college. Talking about school readiness, it seems that early-childhood outcomes vary by family structure. Kim mentioned the result of a study that “analyzes 1,370 mothers in the fragile families and child wellbeing study who were continuously married from the child’s birth to age three” (Kim, 2008, p. 4). It found that three-year-old child who was born from cohabiting mothers have a tendency to show violence and nervous conduct than another child who was born from married mother.

The Effect of Socio-Economic Status on Child’s Achievement

“Socioeconomic status (SES) is often measured as a combination of education, income and occupation. It is commonly conceptualized as the social standing or class of an individual or group” (American Psychological Association, 2017, para 1).

Today in the United States, the discriminations in capital distribution and the quality of life are globally growing. Usually, societies advantage from an increased foundation of socioeconomic biases in order to reduce the gaps in socioeconomic status in the government. But how does this status affects the child’s education?

Research shows that students from low socio economic status develop their academic skills more slowly comparing to those from higher socio economic status. An association exists between academic success and the home environment where low knowledge environments and continuing anxiety and tension atmosphere disturb

a child's academic skills (Eitel, 2015). A family with low social economic status aim to provide the daily bread for its members. Low income cannot provide extra resources for the children to play and to learn. The presence of academic support in a similar house is probably rare. "Children's initial reading competence is correlated with the home literacy environment, number of books owned and parent distress" (Aikens & Barbarin, 2008, p. 2). Yet, impoverished parents may not be able to manage to pay for properties such as educational toys, stories, books, technological resources, or special teachers to push their child forward in his/her academic journey.

Another concern besides books is nutrition, as well as attention. "Nearly 43% of children under 5 in low- and middle-income countries are not getting the nutrition, protection and stimulation they need. This diminishes both the child's potential and sustainable growth for society at large" (UNICEF, n.d., para. 1).

Socioeconomic status (SES) remains a significant issue to those who study early childhood development. This interest derives from a thought that rich parents have enough money to cover all their children needs and to provide facilities. On the other hand, poor parents with low socioeconomic status, lack access to the needed capital and experiences, which expose their children to developmental risks. Research shows that socioeconomic status is related with a wide range of health, cognitive, and socio emotional consequences in children's life from their birth to their adulthood. It impacts their welfare at several stages and effects their own characteristics, their family characteristic too. In their study entitled "socioeconomic status and child development," Bradley and Corwyn (2002) found that "children from low-SES families are more likely to experience growth retardation and inadequate neurobehavioral development in utero. They are more likely to be born prematurely,

at low birth weight, or with asphyxia, a birth defect, a disability, fetal alcohol syndrome, or AIDS” (p. 374).

Economic status also has a huge impact on parents and on their children at the same time. Previous research (American Psychological Association, 2016; Hart, 2016; Pettigrew, 2009) has found that the socioeconomic status of the student is an important predictor of achievement, and that the percentage of students on the free and reduced lunch program (given to poor students in the United States) can serve as a proxy for socioeconomic status (Vanderstel, 2014). Parents on the lower end of the socioeconomic range frequently provide an inferior level of academic support for their children for many reasons. Many of them are not willing to provide a quality time with their child. They place him/her in front of the television for almost the whole day because they are working hard to provide the family’s need and they do not have enough time for him/her. Also, some of them are not able to provide academic resources for their children that would help them develop their skills, for they are really above their budget. Last and not least, these poor parents could lack in feeling responsibility to help their child. They may feel it is not their role, and expect the school to do everything. Instead of doing their best to support him/her in many areas, they could even send him/her to street to beg. Lower socioeconomic status contributes to lower academic performance and slower amounts of educational improvement.

A nationwide study of American kindergarten children found out that “36 percent of parents in the lowest-income quintile read to their children on a daily basis, compared with 62 percent of parents from the highest-income quintile” (Coley, 2002, p. 54). The result of this study shows that the inequality in school readiness is clear when we talk about the economic difference between families. This case does not concern just the student, but it spreads to let the parents be involved too.

Research shows that mother from low socio economic status was related to her child's inattention, disinterest, and lack of cooperation in school. "Low-income parents participate less in schools than higher- income parents despite the benefits of parent involvement" (Savage, 2007, para 1). These parents face many daily issues. Sometimes, we found them loosing abilities to contribute to their children's education because of their unstable daily life. Low socio economic parents can be lack of responsibility, capability or willingness in being engaged in their early child's educational achievement due to a number of barriers that could be demographic, psychological, physical or financial.

Parental Involvement in Arab Nations

It is hard to find studies that show the importance of parental involvement in Lebanese young children educational achievement. Studies and articles written about this subject are so general and do not focus on this main issue. I can conclude about them by saying that most parents seemingly are not involved until their children face a serious problem at preschool/school. Rare studies like the one done by Najla Nusair Bashour in 2016 stated that education in preschool is characterized by the lack of central governmental Lebanese authority that is in charge of setting policies, objectives, criteria, and conditions for preschools. If the ministry of education does not care about making specific curriculum for its young Lebanese students, what can we expect from parents? Today, Lebanese preschools include 33.9% of children ages 3-4 and 61.7% of children aged 4-6 (The Institute for Development, Research, Advocacy, and Applied Care, 2007). In her study, Tutelian (2013) found that 8% of children under-five years of age were left in the care of other children under the age of 10 years during the week prior to the survey. . . The lower the mother/caretaker's level of education is, the more likely this was to happen.

Where the mother/caretaker had no education, 20% of the children they cared for had been left alone with other children under 10 years of age the previous week. On the other hand, where the mother/ caretaker held a university degree, only 4% of the children they cared for had been left with other children under 10 the week before. (p. 6)

Parental Involvement in Lebanon

How do the parents in Lebanon compare in this case? Parents in Lebanon are not just Lebanese people. They are also immigrants and refugee. The Immigrants in Lebanon, a large study of “2,147 children aged 6-12 shows that parents' education is more strongly associated with children's academic achievement than any other premigration attribute” (Child Development Society, 2012, p. 83). But there is not any published Lebanese study done recently that shows the impact of emigrant parents' involvement on their African children who spend their first five years in Lebanese preschool. Migration is a widespread phenomenon in the Middle East, and Lebanon is in the first class of countries who receive migrants. By working in Lebanon, these people hope to send some money home and improve the lives of their family members. But if they are working really hard, is it possible to offer the best for their young children and to help them improve and succeed in school and in life?

A study that concerns the involvement of immigrants and refugee families in their children's schools in the United States, mentioned a lot of barriers and challenges that kept parents from providing meaningful support for their offspring (U.S. Conference of Catholic Bishops, 2016). They can indicate in this case the language issues, cultural expectations, isolation, busy personal lives, family trauma and lack of welcoming atmosphere in some schools. In Lebanon 13 years after the

publication of this article, we still find that these same reasons are common. All these challenges are still facing the Syrian refugees in Lebanon and many more, also.

In Lebanon today, it seems that UNICEF and World Vision are the only agencies that provide us with data about refugee children. In her article entitled “Bringing Learning to Syrian Refugee Children in Lebanon,” Azar (2014) argued about an educational ministry that deals with the serious problems of Syrian students. Many of the younger children struggle to hold a pen. Some of them do not know what it is used for, and others are afraid to touch it or maybe have forgotten how to do it. I tried to find studies that concerned refugee parental involvement in their children’s achievement in Lebanon, but I did not find any. Rare are the studies done in this area and maybe none has been done, or at least none is published. This is briefly what has been found in this area concerning the Lebanese, immigrant and refugee early children in Lebanon, and what is missing is a lot. My study aims to light up on this gap.

In addition to shedding some light on this huge gap, my study focuses on three main types of parental involvement: parental willingness, parental capability and parental understanding of their responsibilities in helping their children. Willing parents are ready and emotionally prepared to help their children. This can be in many areas. Lebanese, refugees and immigrant people who live in Lebanon could be enthusiastic to provide the educational support to their children but they do not know how to do it. No one guided them before or trained them to achieve this task. Also, we cannot ignore that this Arabic nation could have never learned before an extra language other than Arabic. That is why they may struggle with other language as well. On the other hand, some of them may be willing but not able to, and other may

not feel responsible for getting involved in supporting their children, thinking that it is really the school's responsibility, not their own.

Socio-Economic Status in Lebanon

According to Issa (2015, para. 1), "one in four Lebanese live in poverty." Added to that is the fact that all these data (Lebanese Center of Human Rights, 2016; UNHCR, 2012) have been drastically transformed due to the arrival of Syrian displaced. Since most of the Syrian displaced fall into the poor category, this brings us to almost 35 or 40 percent of poor (see for example, Ballout, 2015). No doubt that all these pieces that concern parents have a great influence on early childhood achievement. For all these reasons, I decided to prepare a study that looks at parental roles in early childhood education in Lebanon.

The Syrian crisis in Lebanon is having a deep influence on social constancy in an economy which was previously facing many complications. Additionally, poverty in Lebanon is affected by the conflict once the refugees (Syrian, Palestinian, Iraqis, etc.) are affecting the labor marketplace. The American University of Beirut (AUB) and the United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees in the Near East (UNRWA, 2016), launched a "Survey on the Socioeconomic Status of Palestine Refugees in Lebanon, 2015." It analysis the living conditions and socio-economic status of all Palestine refugees living in Lebanon, and the Palestine refugees who came from Syria in the past five years. This study found out that "65 per cent of Palestine refugees from Lebanon and some 90 percent of PRS live in poverty, including 9 per cent of the PRS living in extreme poverty and unable to meet even their most essential food requirements" (UNRWA, 2016, para.4). Sadly, the result showed that 23.2 per cent of Palestine refugees from Lebanon do not have a current job as well as 52.5 per cent of Palestinian refugees from Syria in Lebanon.

Lebanon is facing daily different kind of issues that impact its economic and social statuses. After six year from the starting date of the Syrian crisis, Lebanon still carries on the impact of this war. The presence of millions of refugees on its land, strained its public finances, facilities and environment. The crisis is anticipated to deteriorate deficiency and poverty occurrence among Lebanese as well as widen income inequality. And as a result of the Syrian war, two hundred thousand of Lebanese people have been pushed into poverty, adding to the erstwhile one million poor, and nearly three hundred thousand lost their jobs, most of them unskilled youth (World Bank, 2016).

On the other hand, life in Lebanon is not easy at all for its citizens and for its visitors. In his article entitled “It’s More Expensive to Live in Lebanon Than in the United Arab Emirates.” “According to Numbeo’s cost of living index, Lebanon is the third most expensive Arab country to live in after Kuwait and Qatar” (Najib, 2015, para. 1). And talking about the quality of life, the numbers show that United Arab Emirates is in the top twenty while Lebanon is in the bottom twenty. It costs a lot to live in Lebanon. In a study about the cost of living in Lebanon, Numbeo (2017) found out how the individual salary is distributed across the expenses in this small country. The results show that people spend monthly 30.8% of their salary on rent, 25.2% at the market. This study also shows that for a private preschool or kindergarten, the fees are an average of \$313 U.S., and international primary school fees cost an average of \$533.25 U.S per child per year (Numbeo, 2017, para. 6). In a country like Lebanon where the minimum wage is \$450 U.S. per month, how can the citizens, immigrants or refugees, manage?

All these studies, theories and articles agree on the importance of the parental involvement in the development of their early children. These first teachers have a lot

to do in the lives of their offspring. Sometimes, life may prevent them from achieving this role or in contrary, it supports them and offers them chances and opportunities to play it by excellence (Spohr, 2014). Capability, responsibly and willingness are three main qualifications that influence the parental performance and lead to a noble early childhood development once they reunite in one parent. Parents are the leaders of their child. When watching over them, they teach them how life works and prepare them to live it successfully. Parents are their children's learning models. Their approaches about education can stimulate theirs and show them how to take charge of their own educational journey in the future (See for example PBS Parents, 2017).

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to find out if there is a significant relationship between Lebanese, immigrant and refugee parental involvement and young children's academic development in Lebanon, especially in a refugee-laden society. This study uses the quantitative method for statistical analysis to determine the result and to answer my research questions numerically.

Quantitative methods stress on objective measurements and numerical analysis of data collected through questionnaires. It focuses on congregate numerical data and generalizing it across groups of people which is the case in my study. I use quantitative methods because I aim to conduct research study to determine the relationship between two independent variables. The research deals in numbers, focuses on numeric and convergent reasoning rather than divergent reasoning.

Through quantitative methods, the data is collected using structured research instruments, the questionnaires. Usually, their results represent a whole population. But in this case, the results are based on a sample of sixty families that are representative of a certain population in Lebanon, and do not cover all. The questionnaires are clear, simple and focused. People's answers are sought and instruments carefully designed before data is collected.

Population and Sample

Grow Early Learning Center—known also as the Philemon Project—focuses on children of low-income immigrant workers and Syrians, providing quality care and an avenue along which Christ may be made known to the children and their parents. The center is the new focal point of the Philemon Project. For many years, the project has offered practical help for migrants and refugees and has kept attention on the issue of migration in Lebanon. This ministry provides Christian-led early childhood development for at-risk poor Lebanese, Syrian refugee, and migrant children. It focuses on children ages one to four years old. Additionally, it works with parents through an adult mentoring program.

Mentoring the parents helps them develop the skills they need to create lasting, healthy, and productive relationships with their children. Today, “Grow Early Learning Center” takes care of seventy young children and is planning to increase the number to be ninety in the future.

I chose this place because it is where I can find a sample from the population I chose to study. Children there come from different nationalities and different backgrounds. Since I am focusing on the effects of parental involvement on immigrant, refugee and Lebanese young children, this place is one of the best. My study concerns sixty students from one preschool with a mixture of nationalities: twenty Lebanese children, twenty Syrian refugee children and twenty immigrant children. I found out that picking children haphazardly in a fair equal distribution—twenty from each nationality—is a good sample. I choose them randomly in order to pick twenty families from each nationality. This center serves more than sixty children. If one of the parents refuses to complete the questionnaires, I have the option to find another one in order to make a demographic balance.

The center—known also as a preschool—is located in a poor and busy Lebanese area. It accepts the students at the age of 1 year old and graduates them at the age of four where they have to attend kindergarten in an elementary school. Most of their parents come from a difficult past to hope in a fruitful future for their children that starts with preschool. Most of them have shared at least once with the staff the challenges that they are facing daily in their lives. These parents are a real sample of the population that lives in our country today. Among them we find the single mother and the widow, the pleased and the depressed, the rich and the poor, the domestic worker and the merchant, the Asian and the African, the Lebanese, the immigrant and the refugee.

Instruments

The instruments used in this study include a demographic questionnaire and three different scales with 20 questions each, focusing on parental involvement in their children's education. Some parents could read or understand the English language. For that reason, I decided to translate the instrument into Arabic so all the parents would understand. First I translated the instruments into Arabic. Then the faculty dean checked them and made corrections before they were sent to the parents.

Demographic Questionnaire

The demographic questionnaire contains eight researcher-designed questions to distinguish between nationality, education, and age of the parents. For the complete instrument, see Appendix A.

Parent Involvement Questionnaire

In order to understand parents' perceptions of their roles and responsibilities, as well as their own abilities in assisting their children with education, I found an

instrument called “Parental Involvement Questionnaire” (Job Involvement Questionnaire, n.d.). I chose this instrument over all others, because it was the most complete and directly related to what I wanted to find out. The instrument has three scales, and I make my own demographic questions (see Appendix A). The objective of these questions is to find out more information about each child’s parents statuses like race, gender, education, occupation, income level, etc. This is to help us understand his/her background in order to find out if it affects his/her development in some ways. On the other hand, the three other scales are Parental involvement capability, Parental feeling of responsibility for participating in the child’s educational program, and Parental willingness to participate in the child’s educational program. I selected this instrument in order to find out if the parents really feel responsible, willing and capable to support their young Lebanese, refugee, or immigrant children academically.

The format of this instrument is easy to fill out for busy parents, as it does not ask them to write or to analyze. It also contains clear, specific, short and focused questions which make the task simple for them. Each of the three scales contains twenty questions. The original scales focused on the skill of reading English, as they were designed for perhaps kindergarten or first grade native speakers of English. I modified the questions slightly to focus more on expressing, understanding, and using the English language as a third language, in early childhood. Parents are asked to just tick their answers without writing a comment because a large number of them cannot write well or they are too busy to write in much detail. Because I am looking for honest answers, I chose to do it this way.

Parents have to respond by choosing between “definitely not, probably not, maybe, not or probably” in a short period of time that could be around three days.

Also, the preschool teachers are be involved in this study that covers one preschool that contains a mixture of Lebanese, immigrant and refugee young students.

Rubric

Each class teacher has to fill out a grading rubric for her students. I had twenty rubrics for the Lebanese students, twenty for immigrants' students and twenty for refugee's students. These are the same students that I have parental data for. The rubric is about the child's attitude, behavior, character, interests, talents, and participation. It shows some main skills that the child supposes to master. It is made per semester. Through it, we can see if the student is being active in class and involved in the class activities.

The rubric shows each student's enthusiasm toward learning, his/her class cooperation and his/her concentration, and identifies if he/she is independent and caring. His/her performance is assessed in the checklist under a rating scale from number 1 till 5. Number 1 means that he/she cannot demonstrate the skill. Number 2 means that he/she demonstrates few elements of the skill. Number 3 means that he/she demonstrates some elements of the skill. Number 4 means he/she demonstrates most elements of the skill. Number 5 means that he/she demonstrates mastery of the skill. For the complete instrument, see Appendix B.

Procedures

In carrying out this study, I first printed the questionnaires in order to distribute them to the parents. Since I am the center's director, it is easy for me to communicate with these people. I know them individually and we had before a lot of general conversations. I planned to welcome them as usual in one or two mornings when they arrived to the preschool to bring their child. I introduced them my case and

I asked them to answer these questions to help me doing this research for my master's thesis. I explained to them that it is optional and I highlighted the ethical considerations.

Parents answered eight demographic questionnaires and the twenty questions for each scale, for a total of 68 questions and the results is entered into R Project in order to find out statistically the amount of parental involvement in their children's development.

The class teachers filled the rubrics for all students who were involved in this study. These rubrics are sorted into 3 groups, by the nationality of the children: Lebanese, immigrants and refugees. The results aim to find out if there is a relationship between parental involvement and children's academic achievement. They let us find out if the parental attitude toward their children affects their academic learning in some way.

Data Analysis

The final results are compared with the descriptive statistics and using analysis of variance (ANOVA) to see how much parents' involvement could have an impact on children academic results, and to study the differences among group means and their associated procedure.

Ethical Considerations

I assure all parents who are going to fill out the questionnaire that they are safe in sharing their responses with me. No one investigates about their status nor blame them, or argue with them about any family issue. They do not write their names or their child's name on any of the documents. The participation is not obligatory, and parents can skip any question or stop answering if they feel uncomfortable. It is a

voluntary participation and they have the freedom to withdraw at any time without penalty. They have to be sure that this task should never affect our relation as director – parent in any way. I never ask any question to them about what they mentioned in the questionnaire. Papers are collected and reported on in groups. This kind of reporting insures anonymity and protection of all individuals involved.

CHAPTER 4

DATA ANALYSIS

Parental Involvement

How much are Lebanese, immigrant and refugee parents involved in their children's lives? To answer this question, I chose to use the qualitative method. It helps to understand the underlying details, attitudes, or stimuli and helps to develop ideas or suppositions for our study.

As director of the preschool under study, I work with the parents of my students every day. These people come from different backgrounds. There is no doubt that each one of them has his/her own story, and it is interesting for me to sit and to listen to each one of them. Before registering their children in the preschool, I ask to meet them in my office to have a little chat about their lives. For me as the director, I believe that it is very important to know what environment these children are coming from. Knowing their past will help us to understand their present and plan for their fruitful future. All parents have something in common: they all want the best for their children. They believe that the educational center provides their children with what they, as parents, cannot provide for them. In our preschool, the children are loved, protected and helped to develop according to their needs and abilities.

A Day in the Preschool

From 7:30 in the morning, the director, the nurse, each class teacher and the nappie changer sit at the main entrance of the preschool, waiting for the children to arrive. Their presence creates an atmosphere of love. They welcome each one of them

individually while the nurse checks and follows up on up the circumstances of the previous night with the parents.

Each class has its own daily schedule that includes time for eating, studying time, playing time and sleeping time. A food specialist is checking on the menu, with the aim to offer the best for these children to grow in a healthy way. All of the teachers are trained weekly to develop their educational skills. As team, we stress the importance of developing our students' fine and large motor skills. That is why we are frequently providing them new toys because we believe that learning is fun. At the end of the day, we provide these children with a daily note that summarizes the details of how their children have spent their day with us.

Parental Involvement by Nationality

As mentioned above, all parents want the best for their children regardless their nationality or life circumstances. This study seeks specific information on how parents view their role in achieving success for their children. As it is difficult to provide an accurate measure of how much the parents actually participate in their child's education, it was decided to assess this qualitatively. As director, I am very close to the parents, and have observed their behavior over the 2 years I have worked in this position. I have seen differences in the way parents deal with their children in the school setting, and these differences seem to differ by nationality. One of the reasons for designing this study was to further explore this phenomenon. For this reason, as an introduction to the data analysis, it seemed helpful to talk in general about the distinctive behaviors of each nationality separately as I have observed and interacted with them over the years. These qualitative observations serve as a basis for understanding the quantitative data which follows. They also serve as a surrogate measure of actual parental involvement.

Lebanese parents are, in my opinion, often the most difficult of the three groups to deal with. They frequently have a defensive attitude when talking about their children. They pretend to offer the best for their children on a daily basis, and expect us to offer the same quality as they do. One typical example of this is about a young lady who earns about 600 U.S dollars per month. She has one little girl who is one-and-a-half years old. This lady comes to my office perhaps three times per week to tell me that she is bringing the best clothes and shoes trends for her daughter, and that she is taking her twice per month to the pediatrician just for a checkup. She often repeats that she is the best type of mother and that she wants the best for her daughter. But in reality, all the signs show that this mother is mainly interested in the outward appearances and not really in the best of the things that truly matter for her child. An example that demonstrates this is that she is not even changing her diaper in the morning, nor even changing her out of her pajamas before bringing her to the preschool, just because she cannot wake up before 7:00 am to prepare her daughter for a new day.

Of course, this example is extreme, but it is typical of problems I often experience with Lebanese parents. Still, these parents are active, participative, and the most willing to question the judgment of the school concerning their children. If the school asks for support, they generally provide it.

Immigrant parents are typically the most committed of the three groups. They do not take the initiative to ask about the importance of their role in the process of their children's development, but once we talk about it, they listen well and they show that they are interested.

We are facing one common issue with a large number of them, however, which is the language. It is hard to communicate with them because they have not

mastered the Arabic language, nor the Lebanese accent. Many of them speak two or three languages with their children at home, and sometimes the child can be confused and not able to understand what the teacher is asking him/her to do. One example of this is a mother who is always ready to meet with me when needed, but sadly, she does not know how to interact with another person when talking. She will listen to me or to the nurse without saying a word. When we ask her a question, she can only answer with three or four words. This can make an obstacle between the parents and the preschool that keeps us from building a good relationship together. This problem of the language barrier is not unique to Lebanon, and is well documented in the literature in other countries (e.g., Sharon, 2013).

Refugee parents are full of amazing stories. Many of them have lived through the worst, unimaginable situations, and they generally seem to have a strong desire to provide the best for their children. They do not want them to experience what they, as parents, lived through before. They have a general belief that education is one of the best ways that can raise them up (Weng & Lee, 2015).

One father registered his daughter in the nursery 3 years ago. On the first day he said that he would not let her spend more than one year with us, because he believes that girls should not receive an education. They should grow up at home until they get married at around 13 years old. But, after only three months from the registration day, the same father came to the nursery and asked to meet the vice president. Crying, he said that he was ready to sell his blood to provide an education for his daughter. I can feel that these people did not recognize before the importance of educating a child. But once they came to Lebanon and started attending schools here and learning from the society, they start understanding that this process is vital. As

a group, I can see them today much more willing than any other people to educate their children.

Lebanese, immigrant and refugee parents are expecting for us to offer the best kind of education to their children. This desire is common between them all, but what differentiates them is their style of interacting with us, of seeing things, of analyzing circumstances, and of what they see as their own role in the process. As a director, these differences do not bother me because I believe that I can learn from each one of them to build my leadership style.

Demographic Analysis by Nationality

Sixty families were involved in this study. While talking about race, all respondents indicated their nationality, and this is shown in Table 1. Twenty of them are Lebanese, twenty are immigrants and the other twenty are refugees. They answered eight demographic questions. The tables below show the answers for each nationality.

Table 1

Race/Ethnicity of Respondents

Nationality	Lebanese	Immigrant	Syrian Refugee
Lebanese	20		
Immigrant		20	
Refugee			20
Total	20	20	20

Table 2 shows the family relationships of those that filled out the survey for the preschool students under study. The data show that 19 Lebanese mothers and just 1 aunt or uncle filled out the questionnaires. This shows that the Lebanese mothers are

generally in charge of what concerns their children in the preschool, and they are involved in the activities of the place where their children attend. The presence of the Lebanese biological mother shows as particularly strong in this survey.

Table 2

Survey Completion

Nationality	Mother	Father	Step Parent	Aunt/Uncle
Lebanese	19			1
Immigrant	12	7		1
Refugee	11	8	1	
Total	42	15	1	2

For the foreigners, however, more fathers participated. For the immigrant people, 12 children had their mothers fill out the questionnaires, 7 others had their fathers doing this job, and one out of twenty had his/her aunt/or uncle fill it out. The immigrant father looks more involved in what concerns his children in the preschool, or maybe, the mother is away because of a certain reason. It is also possible that he filled out the form because he has stronger language or literacy skills.

For the refugee parents, I have experienced that the role of the mother is often less prominent and forceful. The mothers are around, but the father usually plays more of a leadership role. This is a known cultural bias in the Arabic peoples who make up the refugee group, but it also may have to do with the trauma they have been through. In some cases, also, the families are not complete, so there was no option as to who would fill out the form. In total, 11 mothers, 8 fathers and 1 step parent filled out the questionnaires. Some of these mothers in this group are not well educated, and they might find such a task hard for them.

Those who responded to the questionnaire were not particularly old (see Table 3). All of them are between 20 and 40 years old. This means that the parents are still young, but mature enough to play the role of supporting their children's academic growth. It is interesting to note that the Immigrant parents were slightly older than the other two groups of parents. It is possible that this comes from the traditions of marrying and having children at a slightly older age in other parts of the world.

Table 3

Age of Respondents

Nationality	20 – 30 years old	30 – 40 years old
Lebanese	10	9
Immigrant	6	14
Refugee	10	10
Total	26	33

A stable family necessitates the presence of a father and a mother. The results shown in Table 4 indicate that sixteen Lebanese, fourteen refugee and thirteen immigrants out of twenty, live with their spouse.

Table 4

Marital Status of Respondents

Nationality	Single Mom	Married	Widow	Divorced	Separated
Lebanese		16		1	3
Immigrant	4	14	1	1	
Refugee	3	13	2	2	
Total	7	43	3	4	3

It is clear that four of the single immigrant mothers and 3 refugee mothers are raising their children without a husband's support. The total of widows is 3, the divorced are 4 and the separated are 3. Note that these numbers are higher for the immigrants and refugees than for the Lebanese families. The absence of one parent will probably affect the stability of the family in a way or other.

Table 5 shows schooling information for the parents of all three nationalities. The picture it paints is fascinating. It shows that overall; approximately half of the parents who completed this survey had only completed 8th Grade. Of the three groups, the immigrants have had the most education, with fully half of the immigrant parents having had some college courses. The refugee parents were the least educated, with 8 refugee parents who did not complete elementary schooling, and only 12 out of 20 who had completed Grade 8. In this case, it is hard or maybe impossible for them to support their children's academic development.

Table 5

Highest Educational Degree of Respondents

Nationality	No schooling completed	Completed 8 th grade	Some high school, no diploma	High school graduate, diploma or the equivalent	Some college credit, no degree
Lebanese	2	10	5	1	2
Immigrant	3	5	2		10
Refugee	8	12			
Total	13	27	7	1	12

Table 5 is a little confusing, because it includes the data from the one who filled out the survey, not from both parents. So it does not give a clear picture as to what might be a gender bias in education. The Lebanese surveys were all completed by women, for example, so that shows the level of education of the women. The other groups had many men who filled out the survey, so this might not be comparable. In any case, it is clear that the educational level is fairly low across all three of the groups in this study, and this likely affects the parents' ability to support academic achievement for their children.

Table 6 shows that most of the parents (52 out of 57, or 91%) who answered this question on the survey are working in different places in order to earn money to survive in Lebanon. Of all the respondents, there was only one stay-at-home mother, and she was among the Lebanese. All the other parents, whether male or female, were looking for work if they were not already employed. This also affects parental willingness and ability to support their children's education.

Table 6

Job of Respondents

Nationality	Employed for wages	Self-employed	Out of work and looking for work	Out of work but not currently looking for work	Domestic worker
Lebanese	11	2	2	1	1
Immigrant	14	4	2		
Refugee	11	5			4
Total	36	11	4	1	5

In my study, speaking English is one of the important skills that parents need to master in order to support their children’s academic development. This is because the preschool operates in English, so any homework requires someone who speaks English to assist them with it. Table 7 shows that of the 60 parents involved in this study, 16 parents never speak this language. This group is not be able to support their children in academic tasks requiring language use. Over half, or 34 of the 60, speak a little English on a daily basis. Only 10 claim to speak English a lot.

It is interesting to compare the language numbers by nationality. The Lebanese parents all speak at least a little English. All but one parent from the Immigrant group also claims to speak English at least a little, with 3 speaking it well. In the Refugee group, however, none of the parents claimed to speak English well. Fully three-fourths of them claim they never speak English. It is clear to see that this group have communication difficulties in English, though they might be able to at least communicate with the school in Arabic better than the Immigrant group.

Table 7

Respondents English Speaking

Nationality	Never	A little	A lot
Lebanese		13	7
Immigrant	1	16	3
Refugee	15	5	
Total	16	34	10

Table 8 shows that the approximate income average for the parents in this study is not high. The Lebanese are earning slightly more than the Immigrant group, but there is not a huge difference, except at the lowest level. Mostly, it is the Refugee group that is suffering from earning the lowest income in Lebanon.

Table 8

Approximate Average Household Income per Month for Respondents

Nationality	Less than \$400	Between \$400 and \$600	Between \$600 and \$1000	Between \$1000 and \$1500	Above \$1500
Lebanese	1	11	6	1	1
Immigrant	4	10	3	2	
Refugee	8	12			
Total	13	33	9	3	1

Parental Capability

Table 9 presents the mean scores of the parents in this study for feelings of capability of being involved in their children's education. Analysis of variance of the data showed that Lebanese parents had significantly higher ($p < .01$) feelings of capability regarding their ability to be involved in their child's academic instruction than both the Immigrant and Refugee groups, who were not significantly different from each other.

Table 9

Parental Feelings of Capability for Involvement in Child's Academic Development

Nationality	M	SD	N
Lebanese	3.99*	.65	16
Immigrant	3.38	.76	16
Refugee	2.46	.17	20

Note. * $p < .01$ Lebanese was different from both Immigrant and Refugee

The mean in Table 9 for the Lebanese participants (3.99) shows that Lebanese parents feel *Capable* toward their involvement in their children's academic development. They have the ability to provide different kinds of support for their children. If we look back at the average of the parents' salary in Table 8, we can see that of those who filled out the questionnaires, just 5% of them earn less than \$400 dollars per month, 55% earn between \$400 and \$600, 30% earn between \$600 and \$1000, and 5% earn more than \$1500. With the addition of their spouse's salary (the parent who did not fill out the questionnaires), this is a reasonable monthly wage. The sum of money that this family receives per month could be enough to identify them as capable parents. Of course, capability is not only measured in financial terms, but poverty tends to be associated with inability to do well in academic areas,

Concerning the activities that do not demand money to be completed like reading, telling, drawing, etc., Lebanese parents also feel capable to be involved. Their language ability may contribute to this, though they were not particularly more highly educated than the other groups of parents.

Immigrant parents see themselves as less capable than Lebanese parents. Their mean (3.38) shows that they feel *Probably Capable* toward their involvement in their

children's academic development. If we look at the average of their salaries (those who filled out the questionnaires), we can see that 20% of them earn less than \$400 per month, 50% earn between \$400 and \$600, 15% earn between \$600 and \$1000, and only 10% earn between \$1000 and \$1500. Maybe they are not capable as much as the Lebanese parents, but they are still getting an acceptable level of earning power, which provides confidence, along with the ability to pay the bills.

Concerning the activities that do not demand money to be completed, like reading, telling, drawing, etc., immigrant parents also feel that they are probably not capable to be involved. This let me think that these parents lost self-confidence because of their life circumstances.

Refugee parents are the ones who clearly label themselves as less capable. With their mean (2.46), they classify themselves as parents who are *Probably not Capable* of providing the academic support their children need. Statistics show that of those who filled out the questionnaires, 40% of them earn less than \$400 per month, and 60% of them earn between \$400 and \$600. These numbers explain to us why these parents are not capable of supporting their child's academic development in such an expensive country like Lebanon where the minimum wage is \$450 US.

Concerning the activities that do not demand money to be completed, like reading, telling, drawing, etc., refugee parents also feel *Probably not Capable* to be involved. Given their low level of language skills and their low level of language skills, even if they had no concerns with trauma or single-parent households, this is not entirely surprising.

Figure 1 shows the same data on parental feelings of ability to participate in their children's education in a boxplot, which highlights the Standard Deviation. Note that both the Lebanese and the Immigrants varied widely in their feelings about

capability, but the Refugees had little variation: they were rather all fairly uniformly low in their assessment of their own abilities.

Figure 1. Parental feelings of capacity for participation.

Parental Responsibility

Table 10 shows how much parents feel responsible for being involved in their children's academic development. Data show that the Lebanese felt significantly more responsible in this area than the other groups ($p < .01$). With a mean of 4.13, their answers demonstrate that they feel *Responsible* to be involved in the process of educating their children. Data showed that they feel responsible in supporting their children and in cooperating with the preschool administration.

Table 10

Parental Feelings of Responsibility for Involvement in Child's Academic Development

Nationality	M	SD	N
Lebanese	4.13*	.79	3
Immigrant	3.45	.53	2
Refugee	3.11	.19	7

Note. $p < .01$, Lebanese different from both of the other groups.

With a mean equal to 3.45, Immigrant parents feel that they are *Probably Responsible* in this process of supporting their children academically. Their answers demonstrate that they cannot be or they doubt that they are completely responsible in their children's academic achievement.

Analyzing the Refugee group, several explanations are in order. First, while their score was not significantly different from that of the Immigrants, their behavior and life situation makes them somewhat different, and might mean they need to be treated differently. The parental responsibility questionnaire topics require that the parents to be educated enough; otherwise they cannot show a strong feeling responsibility. Table 7 showed that Refugees have a low level of education that prevents them from passing quality academic information to their children. Table 8 shows that they had the lowest average of income which could prevent them from doing educational activities with their children. Getting a low mean (3.11), is not surprising in this case.

Figure 2 shows that the Lebanese parents feel responsible to participate in their children's educational process. Note that both the Lebanese and the Immigrants

varied widely in their feelings about responsibility, but the Refugees had little variation.

Figure 2. Standard deviation of parental responsibility.

Parental Willingness

Table 11 shows that both Lebanese and Refugee parents feel *willing* to be involved in their children's academic development. This is the first time where we can see that Refugees are getting a higher level of involvement, similar to what the Lebanese parents show. This is important because it shows that these people want to play a vital role in this process. Their desire is well shown here, regardless of their feelings of lack of ability to achieve this goal. As well as the Lebanese people, they are willing to cooperate with the preschool administration, to help their children to complete their assignments, and to provide them educational materials.

The Immigrant parents in this case are significantly less willing ($p < .01$) than the Lebanese and the Refugee groups to help their children in academic achievements. With a mean equal to 3.35, they demonstrated that they feel *Probably Willing* toward this task.

Table 11

Parental Feelings of Willingness for Involvement in Child's Academic Development

Nationality	M	SD	N
Lebanese	4.14	.80	18
Immigrant	3.35*	.67	19
Refugee	4.12	.18	17

Note. Immigrants were different from the other two groups, $p < .01$.

Note (see Figure 3) that not only were the Refugee parents willing to help equally as much as the Lebanese parents, they were also unanimous in their response. This group as a whole believes strongly in this, with very little variation among them. The Lebanese and the Immigrants, on the other hand, were much more varied in their responses, with certain individuals feeling very willing to help, and others not feeling willing to help much at all. This may relate to their feelings about the school's role versus their own, or may reflect their personal time availability, since most are working, and probably feeling quite busy.

Figure 3. Standard deviation of parental willingness.

Academic Achievement Analysis

Each class teacher filled out a grading rubric for her students. There are about twenty rubrics for the Lebanese students, twenty for immigrants' students and twenty for refugee's students. The results show the rating of each child in five distinct areas: Attitude, Behavior, Character, Interests and talents, and Participation in class activities. The grading rubric uses numbers from 1 to 5. Number 1 means that the child cannot demonstrate the skill. Number 2 means that he/she demonstrates few elements of the skill. Number 3 means that he/she demonstrates some elements of the skill. Number 4 means he/she demonstrates most elements of the skill. Number 5 means that he/she demonstrates mastery of the skill. In Table 12, we can see the overall means of each nationality for the grading rubric.

Table 12

Grading Rubric Means by Nationality

Nationality	M
Lebanese	4.41
Immigrant	4.34
Refugee	3.89

The overall results show that the Lebanese children demonstrated most elements of the required skills, and the immigrant children did, as well. Refugee children demonstrated only some elements of the required skills.

Table 13 shows that the Lebanese and the Immigrant students did not score significantly differently when it comes to the grading rubric. Although the Lebanese scored higher, this difference was not significant. Both groups, however, scored significantly higher than the Refugee students.

Table 13

Children's Grading Rubric Means by Paired Nationalities

Immigrant – Lebanese	0.00504 **
Refugee –Lebanese	0.001***
Refugee – Immigrant	0.14026

Note. *p <0.01. The difference between immigrant and Lebanese children is significant as well as the difference between refugee and Lebanese students.

Rubric Analysis by Subject

Because of the importance of understanding the different aspects of development, and because of the lack of clarity in how the Refugee group might score in each of the areas covered by the grading rubric, it was deemed important to assess the rubric by nationality in each of the subject areas. This shows whether the significant difference noted above is across all areas of development, or is restricted to certain aspects.

Table 14 and Figure 4 establish that Lebanese and immigrant children show a good attitude. They demonstrate most element of the skill. Refugees are having more approaches challenges. They demonstrate some element of the skills.

Table 14

Grading Rubric Means by Nationality and Attitude

Nationality	Attitude Mean
Lebanese	4.47
Immigrant	4.47
Refugee	3.85

Figure 4. Children's attitude.

Table 15 and Figure 5 show that Lebanese children as well as Immigrant children were able to demonstrate most elements of the skills. For the Refugee children, the mean shows that they demonstrated only some elements of the skills being evaluated.

Table 15

Grading Rubric Means by Nationality and Behavior

Nationality	Behavior Mean
Lebanese	4.30
Immigrant	4.21
Refugee	3.75

Figure 5. Children's behavior.

Table 16 and Figure 6 show the grading rubric assessment in the area of Character. Table 16 shows that that Lebanese, immigrant and refugee children all were able to demonstrate most elements of the skill with only a minor difference. This suggests that the developmental and linguistic differences that Refugee children struggle with may not extend to areas such as Character. This is good news.

Table 16

Grading Rubric Means by Nationality and Character

Nationality	Attitude Mean
Lebanese	4.35
Immigrant	4.32
Refugee	4.03

Figure 6. Children's character.

Table 17 and Figure 7 show the grading rubric results in the area of Interests and Talents. Results show that Lebanese and immigrant children demonstrate most elements of the skills, but the refugee children demonstrate only some elements of the skill. Looking more closely at the question, this may be because of the language skills

involved in demonstrating these skills, which are clearly lacking in the Refugee children.

Table 17

Grading Rubric Means by Nationality and Interests and Talents

Nationality	Interest and Talents Mean
Lebanese	4.35
Immigrant	4.50
Refugee	3.84

Figure 7. Children's attitudes and talents.

Table 18 and Figure 8 show results in the area of Participation. Here we see that Lebanese children demonstrate mastery of the skill. Their score is not so much higher, but the average suggests total mastery of this area. It seems that they are considered the standard for the teachers, of what is expected. The Immigrant and Refugee students both demonstrated most elements of the skills. It is encouraging that the Refugee population is not far behind in this area of Participation, which likely will help to increase the other aspects in the near future.

Table 18

Grading Rubric Means by Nationality and Participation

Nationality	Nationality and Participation Mean
Lebanese	4.58
Immigrant	4.20
Refugee	3.95

Figure 8. Children's participation.

Table 19 shows that overall, the Lebanese children's grading rubric mean is 4.41. This number shows that Lebanese children demonstrate most elements of the skills. We can conclude that the Lebanese students' academic level is high and close to excellence. These people who live in their country appear less worried about managing their daily life compared to other foreign people. It seems that they are supporting their children's development process. If they are not, they are accomplishing the necessary support for the children through some other means, and this is shown through their little ones' solid academic performance. Lebanese students are developing their skills well, and they are showing meaningful progress.

Table 19

Grading Rubric Overall Means by Nationality

Nationality	Attitude	Behavior	Character	Interests	Talents and Participation	Mean
Lebanese	4.5	4.3	4.4	4.4	4.6	4.41
Immigrant	4.5	4.2	4.3	4.5	4.2	4.34
Refugee	3.9	3.8	4.0	3.9	4.0	3.89*

Note. Refugees significantly different from both groups, * $p < .001$.

Immigrant children have an overall grading rubric mean of 4.34. This number is also close to the perfect score of 5 and shows that these children demonstrate most elements of the skills. This score shows a very acceptable level of competence, and is not significantly different from the Lebanese children. There is no single area of the rubric where differences are demonstrated between the two groups.

These people who left their country willingly and came to Lebanon have been living in better conditions than other foreign people. Their status does not seem to make a huge impact on their relationship with their children who are developing their academic skills well. This sample of the population is certainly navigating multiple cultures adequately, while still maintaining a good relationship with their children and this is shown through their academic results.

Refugee children's scores on the grading rubric had an overall mean of 3.89. This number is significantly lower than the other two groups, which shows that the children are not quite able to compete with their peers. Immigrant children face barriers because of their parent's status, language barriers, and a higher percentage of broken families, as well as all the other factors that affect their lives as immigrants. They may be unaware of their family's status, but it seems that it is affecting them in

many ways. Immigrant parental involvement in the process of their children development also looks weak, at least partly due to linguistic and educational problems, but this does not directly correlate with the lower grades.

Correlation analyses showed some correlation between parental feelings of capability and willingness to participate. Multiple regression analysis, however, yielded no significant model predicting outcomes based on parental involvement or nationality.

Conclusion

All parents want to see their children succeeding in life. These sixty families are a small sample of three populations that live in Lebanon. They may not have a high education level or a high income, but there is no doubt that they wish the best for their children. Regardless of their direct involvement in their child's developmental process, they still desire to provide him/her with the best. Sadly, the desire by itself cannot be enough to reach this target, which is why actions need to accompany the desire.

There was no direct statistical correlation found between parental involvement and student grades. This may be because the model is extremely completed, and the students are not actually beginning on a level playing field. For the Refugee population, there are inequalities in language and family background that even the most involved and helpful parents may not be able to make up for. Some children may need their parents' help more than others. And it may be that those who need the most help have parents who are very willing, but who are not necessarily capable of giving the kind of help that is needed.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

It is not easy at all to be a parent. This mission demands wise people to accomplish academic goals and to educate their children in the right way. Some have easy access to advice about raising their children, and others find it enough to imitate any sample of parents. Many parents feel overwhelmed and overworked. Parenting needs responsible father and mother who are willing to work as duo for the best of their family and their children development. Issues in families can have bad influences on all its members and especially on the children. Here comes the role of strong parents.

Parental Status: Responsible, Capable and Willing?

In brief, the findings of this study are interesting, but inconclusive. There are differences between the three nationalities in attitudes toward parental support of students. Lebanese parents feel more responsible, capable and willing than Refugee parents at all times, and occasionally have superior scores to the Immigrant population, as well, though they often scored the same. Immigrant parents show a high level of attitude toward their involvement in their children academic development which is generally similar to the Lebanese parents, but not identical. Refugee parents are willing to support their children in all ways, but sadly they see themselves as probably not capable and feel that it is not really their responsibility.

In terms of academic results, the Lebanese and the Immigrant population scored statistically the same, while the Refugee group scored significantly lower on

the grading rubric. The results were statistically significant, and though the difference was not extremely large, the interpretation was clearly that this group was not as advanced overall, though in areas such as Character, their scores were not much lower.

To answer the original research questions asked in this study:

1. How much are Lebanese, immigrant and refugee parents involved in their children's lives, and does this show in their academic achievement?

Lebanese, immigrant and refugee parents are involved in their children's lives in different levels. Lebanese show a big interest in being part of their children's development process. Immigrants parents are willing to participate, but they are not taking always the initiative to do that. Refugee parents are willing to be involved, but their involvement still shy for different reasons.

2. Are there differences in attitudes toward parental involvement based on demographic status?

Demographic status shows differences in attitude toward parental involvement based on demographic status. The Lebanese demographic status is more stable and quiet similar to the immigrant one. Refugee status is showing a lower level of constancy, of educational background and of socioeconomic status.

3. Are there differences in parental involvement (capable, responsible, and willing) in Lebanese, immigrant, and refugee children?

Lebanese and immigrant parents feel capable and responsible toward their involvement in their children's academic development. Data shows that

refugee parents who feel probably not capable are willing to be an active agent in this process despite their feeling of incapability.

4. Is there a correlation between parental involvement and children's academic achievement by nationality?

The correlation between parental involvement and children's academic achievement by nationality is not significant. Data show that some correlation between parental feelings of capability and willingness to participate, however, it is not an important model to be considered in this case.

Implications

Data shows that all parents are willing to be involved in their children developmental process, but especially the Refugee parents. It is clear that they love their children and want to provide them the best. Obstacles that prevent them from reaching this goal are not few. Life was not fair with some of them and hard enough for others, and this makes them passive in some ways. Their involvement was not found to make a predictable statistical difference in the children's performance; however, the concepts were so complex that this may have blurred the math. Qualitatively, it is clear that the students who need the most help from home often have parents who are the least qualified to provide it.

The desire for parental involvement is present in all populations, though least of all in the Immigrants, who are mostly working parents, and may find that the Lebanese school system is giving them more than they ever might have expected if they were home in their country. In any case, the practical steps are not generally

followed through. Some parents do not feel they need to be more involved, others simply don't feel capable.

I do not know if we can blame them or expect them to be more responsible. Their problem is that they have been born or lived in the wrong place. If these three ample of populations were found in a wealthy country, I think that the data analysis would show different results. If they are not completing their parenting job well, it is perhaps because they are working hard to survive in an expensive country like Lebanon. This lifestyle puts a huge burden on their shoulders that keeps them from enjoying their role as parents.

Responsible parents do not have to find special ways to make their children happy. Sometimes, they have to be the voice of reason or discipline. When children refuse to obey, to follow the instructions, to go to school, to do their assignments, or to do things that will help them grow in a healthy manner, parents should be the ones who direct the situation. Simple behavior can put any child at risk. He/she could insist on watching movies for a long period of time, or to eat always junk food or a huge amount of sugar for example. Tired parents can easily give in to their children's desires. The stresses of life can make them feel down and unable to play a qualified parental role. They could be native citizens who have lost hope in their country, or immigrants who left their land to go to the unknown, or refugees who have lost everything. As they find themselves in demanding situations, they may be struggled in completing this task toward their children.

Parents need to be their child's best fan by providing encouragement, provision, understanding, money, education, etc. But sadly some of them neglect this important role because of their difficult life circumstances, or simply because of their ignorance. Maybe no one taught them before that as their child's first teacher, they

can shape their child's future from his/her early years. Their wise involvement counts the most while parenting. We can also find unwilling parents who ignore their responsibilities as caregivers. They allow their children to grow as uncivilized savages instead of educating them in an appropriate way. They harm them instead of educating them. Children need to be loved unconditionally, but willingness to discipline and shape their character is a must.

When parents are not capable to love and take care of themselves, they are not able to love and take care of their children. People who have been wounded once, often lose the sense of love in their life. War and terror has affected our Arab population today and it leaves its traces on their feelings, behavior, thoughts, and their way of educating. Immigrants or refugees could develop a negative conception of themselves and their bodies and extend this shame to their children. They cannot pass on affection and tenderness to those who surround them. Sometimes we see them incapable of caring for other people, especially the youngest ones. Faced with the emotional discomfort, parents unconsciously detach themselves from their child.

Recommendations for Parents

Parents are their children's first and best teachers. Even if they are not highly educated themselves. But what can/should parents do that they are not doing already? Here is a list of recommendations.

1. Parents need to have a stable emotional, cognitive and social status themselves. They need to as much as possible be the parent, and help the child develop normal social, cognitive, and emotional skills.

2. Simple but necessary milestones should be taught to the children during their early age. It is the parents' job to teach them age-appropriate skills in order to permit them become autonomous.
3. As first teacher, mother and father could attend English sessions in order to help their children completing their school assignments.
4. Parents can attend parental guidance sessions—offered by the Lebanese Ministry of Affaires for free—to help them serve their children and raise them well.
5. Parents need to always look for something original and special to support their children's development. They can let them be involved in the daily life activities in order to teach them many skills.
6. Parents are asked to keep a positive attitude toward their status and to not reflect on their miserable circumstances, but on what is the best for their children.
7. Parents need to manage their well time to be fair with their children, to give them their rights, try something new, use effective educational strategies, enjoy living with them, laugh with them, play with them and grow daily together.

Recommendations for Preschool Directors

As a preschool director, I have learned a lot of things and I would like to share one main lesson with my colleagues. Sometimes, and as educated people, we expect that all people should know what we already know. When we see parents using unacceptable educational skills with their children, we often start blaming them. But

the reality is different and we can discover it after one or two meetings with them. When we listen to them, we may find out that they do not know how to raise their children. Maybe no one taught them or no one guided them. They could think that hitting, screaming, neglecting, ignoring, etc. are the best disciplinary strategies to use with their child. And the worst this is that they may think that they are playing their parental role with excellence.

Here are some key recommendations I would make to other preschool directors, especially for dealing with less-privileged students in the Lebanese context.

1. Listen. Don't judge any parent without hearing his/her story and finding out what is behind it.
2. Train. Parents want to be qualified, but they often don't know how to do it. Consider providing an adult mentoring program in preschool that will teach the parenting skills you find lacking.
3. Provide support. Budget for a monthly workshop with a counselor, social worker and/or a psychologist. This helps parents overcome depression, love themselves and feel valuable.
4. Bring them to the school. Invite them to an open house event. Let them spend time with their children in preschool. There, they can learn from the educators better ways of dealing with the child.
5. Network. Cooperate with organizations that mentor people (like UNESCO and Himaya for example). They can provide parents with free workshops, fellowships, training, and much more.

Recommendations for Researchers

My study covered a small sample of three populations of people who live in a busy, poor Lebanese area. I am sure that a larger population could show more complicated issues that families are facing on a daily basis. If someone were to repeat this study with a larger population, they should also clarify the educational levels and language skills of both parents, as this would yield better data.

Additional research could be done with grades, and at higher levels, including elementary school. The lack of significant relationships that showed up in this small preschool study might be overcome if a more complex analysis were done of grades and involvement, including actual time spent with children, not only feelings of willingness or capability.

I recommend the researchers play a significant role in the future by reflecting on the other side of my study in order to find out why parents are less capable, responsible or willing to be involved in their children's academic development. With clarity on those answers, parental support or increased educational support could be improved. I am sure that once we know in details the causes that prevent them from being better parents, we can be able to support them as much as we can. From the workplace, as educators, we can teach people to make a difference in their homes and in their families. Mentoring parents can save the world and create an exceptional generation.

Conclusion

Above all else, it is important to remember that every child is unique. He/she deserves to live each moment in life and to enjoy it to the maximum. Sometimes, circumstances are stronger than our will, and this is normal. We are human, and no one can be perfect. But let us remember that time flies. Yesterday will never come

back, and tomorrow is not guaranteed. Our children are growing and we are growing, too. What we can do for them today, we may not be able to do tomorrow. So let us enjoy every moment together with them, and seek always for the best that helps our children become all that they can be.

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APPENDIX A

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear parents,

I am doing this research for my master's thesis. Your help is so appreciated. Kindly, you are asked to fill out these questions within three days maximum and return them back to me. Because I respect your privacy, I will not ask you to write your child's name, but kindly mention your nationality. I would like to assure you that no one will investigate about your status nor blame you. I will never ask you for any clarification concerning your answer. Also, you can skip a question if you feel uncomfortable to respond to it. It is a voluntary participation and you have the freedom to withdraw at any time without penalty. I guarantee that this task will never affect our relation as director – parent in any way. I appreciate your support. Sincerely, Mireille Feghaly.

Part I-Demographic Questionnaire

Directions: For each question, please select only one answer. If more than one answer is true for you or your family, please select the answer that fits best.

- 1- What is your relationship to the student?
 - Mother
 - Father
 - Step Parent
 - Grandparent
 - Aunt/Uncle
 - Foster Parent
 - Other

- 2- What is your current age?
[] Please enter

- 3- Which race/ethnicity best describes you? (Please choose only one.)
 - Lebanese
 - Immigrant
 - Syrian Refugee
 - Other

- 4- What is your marital status?
 - Single mom
 - Married
 - Widowed
 - Divorced
 - Separated

- 5- What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed?
 - No schooling completed
 - Completed 8th grade
 - Some high school, no diploma
 - High school graduate, diploma or the equivalent
 - Some college credit, no degree

- 6- Are you currently...?
 - Employed for wages
 - Self-employed
 - Out of work and looking for work
 - Out of work but not currently looking for work

- A domestic worker
- Military
- Retired
- Unable to work

7- How much English do you speak in daily life?

- Never
- A little
- A lot

8. What is your approximate average household income per month?

- Less than \$400
- Between \$400 and \$600
- Between \$600 and \$1000
- Between \$1000 and \$1500
- Above \$1500

PART II – Parental Involvement Capability

القسم 2- قدرة الأهل على المشاركة

Directions: Parents can be involved in their child's educational program in several ways. Read at the activities below and tell how capable you feel in carrying out each activity. Circle the number of your answer.

توجيهات: يمكن للأهل أن يشاركوا في برنامج طفلم التعليمي في عدة طرق. اقرأ الى النشاطات في الأسفل وأختر كيف تشعر أنك قادر على تنفيذ كل نشاط منها. ضع دائرة حول الرقم الذي يمثل جوابك.

Definitely not Capable: DNC بالتأكيد غير قادر
 Probably not Capable: PNC ربما غير قادر
 Probably Capable: PC محتمل ان أقدر
 Capable: C قادر
 Very Capable: VC قادر جداً

Activities	DNC	PNC	PC	C	VC
1. Reading to my child in English. اقرأ لطفلي باللغة الانكليزية.	1	2	3	4	5
2. Helping my child to understand words in English stories. أساعد طفلي في فهم الكلمات باللغة الانكليزية.	1	2	3	4	5
3. Listening to and talking about stories with my child. أستمع وأتحدث الى طفلي عن القصص المقروؤة.	1	2	3	4	5
4. Talking and studying the pictures modeling in storybooks. أتحدث الى طفلي وأدرس معه الصور النموجية في القصص المصورة.	1	2	3	4	5
5. Talking about the main idea in a story or English book. أتحدث عن الفكرة الرئيسية في القصة أو في كتاب اللغة الانكليزية.	1	2	3	4	5
6. Helping the child tell a story in English. أساعد طفلي على تلاوة قصة باللغة الانكليزية.	1	2	3	4	5
7. Telling or drawing stories based on family experiences. أخبر وأرسم قصص مستندة على تجارب الأسرة.	1	2	3	4	5

Activities	DNC	PNC	PC	C	VC
8. Helping my child to identify words or symbols in different places (e. g. on cereal boxes or in dictionaries) أساعد طفلي على التعرف الى الكلمات أو الرموز في أماكن مختلفة (مثلاً: على علب الأطعمة أو على القواميس).	1	2	3	4	5
9. Teaching my child about story characteristics (plot, theme, setting, characters) أعلم طفلي عن خصائص القصص (حبكة القصة، الفكرة الرئيسية، الوضع الأساسي، الشخصيات).	1	2	3	4	5
10. Finding out about child's reading progress. اكتشاف مدى تقدم طفلي في القراءة.	1	2	3	4	5
11. Teaching my child how to use resources (encyclopedias, dictionaries, almanacs, atlas) أعلم طفلي استخدام المراجع (موسوعات، قواميس، التقويم، الاطلس).	1	2	3	4	5
12. Providing books and magazines for my child to read in English. أؤمن كتب ومجلات ليقرأها لطفلي طفلي باللغة الانكليزية.	1	2	3	4	5
13. Showing a positive attitude toward reading in English. أظهر موقف ايجابي تجاه القراءة باللغة الانكليزية.	1	2	3	4	5
14. Helping my child to write his/her name or the alphabets or the numbers from 1 to 10. أساعد طفلي على كتابة اسمه/اسمها أو احرف الابجدية أو الأرقام من 1 الى 10.	1	2	3	4	5
15. Providing experience for my child to read or speak in English. أؤمن لطفلي تجربة تحوله القراءة أو التحدث باللغة الانكليزية.	1	2	3	4	5
16. Helping my child learn what words mean. أساعد طفلي على تعلم ما تعنيه الكلمات.	1	2	3	4	5
17. Controlling amount of television my child watches. اتحكم بوقت مشاهدة الطفل للتلفاز.	1	2	3	4	5
18. Working in the preschool as an aide, parent tutor, parent volunteer, teacher, or other such jobs. أعمل في الحضانه كمساعد، معلم خاص، متطوع، مدرس، أو القيام بأية أعمال أخرى.	1	2	3	4	5
19. Helping to reinforce what my child's teacher has taught. أساعد على تعزيز ما تدرس معلمة طفلي.	1	2	3	4	5
20. Setting standards for speech in the home. أضع معيار للغة التخاطب في المنزل.	1	2	3	4	5

PART III– Parental Responsibility for Participating in Child's Educational Program

مسؤولية الوالدين بالمشاركة في برنامج الطفل التربوي

Directions: Which of these activities do you feel parents should accept responsibility for in the preschool's educational program? Circle the number of your answer.

توجيهات: في أي من هذه الأنشطة تشعر أنه على الوالدين تحمل مسؤولية في البرنامج التعليمي في مرحلة ما قبل المدرسة؟ ضع دائرة حول الرقم الذي يمثل جوابك.

Definitely not Responsible: DNR
Probably not Responsible: PNR
Probably Responsible: PR
Responsible: R
Very Responsible: VR

بالتأكيد غير مسؤول
ربما غير مسؤول
محتمل أن أكون مسؤولاً
مسؤول
مسؤول جداً

Activities	DNR	PNR	PR	R	VR
1. Helping the child with homework or any kind of preschool activities. أساعد الطفل في اتمام فروضه أو أي نوع من النشاطات المدرسية.	1	2	3	4	5
2. Working in the preschool as an aide, parent tutor, parent volunteer, teacher, or other such jobs. أعمل في الحضانه كمساعد, معلم خاص, متطوع, مدرس, أو القيام بأية أعمال أخرى.	1	2	3	4	5
3. Arranging workshops with my child's teacher about reading or speaking in English. أنظيم ورش عمل مع معلمة طفلي عن القراءة أو التكم بالغة الانكليزية.	1	2	3	4	5
4. Going to workshops or other such educational activities for parents at preschool. أذهب الى ورش عمل أو أي مشغل آخر كتدريب تربوي للأهل في الحضانه.	1	2	3	4	5
5. Taking part in parent- teacher association meetings. أشارك في اجتماعات لجنة الأهل.	1	2	3	4	5
6. Helping my child learn through the use of educational materials at home (games, magazines, books, newspapers). أساعد طفلي على التعلّم من خلال استخدام مواد تربوية في المنزل (الالعاب، مجلات، كتب، صحف)	1	2	3	4	5
7. Taking my child to places of educational interest; for example, museums, libraries, art galleries. اصطحب طفلي الى أماكن ذات فائدة تربوية مثلاً: المتاحف، المكتبات، المعارض الفنية.	1	2	3	4	5
8. Controlling the amount of time my child spends watching TV and the types of programs. أتحكم بوقت مشاهدة طفلي للتلفاز وبأنواع البرامج.	1	2	3	4	5
9. Reading aloud to my child every day. أقرأ لطفلي بصوت مرتفع يومياً.	1	2	3	4	5
10. Letting my child see me reading each day. أتعمد بأن يراي طفلي وأنا أقرأ يومياً.	1	2	3	4	5
11. Helping my child add English words to his/her speaking vocabulary. أساعد طفلي على اضافة كلمات انكليزية على مفرداته المستخدمة في المحادثة.	1	2	3	4	5
12. Setting standards for speech in the home that will enable my child to communicate easily in English outside the home. أضع معايير للتخاطب في المنزل والتي تمكن طفلي من التحدث بسهولة بالغة الانكليزية خارج البيت.	1	2	3	4	5
13. Encouraging conversation in the home. أشجع المحادثة في المنزل.	1	2	3	4	5
14. Providing my child with a collection of English books selected with his/her interests in mind. أؤمن لولدي مجموعة من الكتب الانكليزية المختارة بحسب اهتماماته الفكرية.	1	2	3	4	5
15. Writing or telling English stories based on family experiences. أكتب أو أقرأ قصص بالغة الانكليزية مستندة على تجارب الأسرة.	1	2	3	4	5
16. Monitoring my child's reading and speaking progress in English. أراقب تقدّم طفلي في القراءة والتحدّث بالغة الانكليزية.	1	2	3	4	5

Activities	DNR	PNR	PR	R	VR
17. Encouraging my child to read or speak English every day. أشجع طفلي على القراءة والتكلم باللغة الانكليزية يومياً.	1	2	3	4	5
18. Helping my child with reference books (i. e., dictionaries, encyclopedias, almanacs, atlas) أساعد طفلي في استعمال كتب المراجع (مثلاً: القواميس, الموسوعات, التقاويم, الاطلس).	1	2	3	4	5
19. Working with my child to reinforce what the teacher has taught. أعمل مع طفلي على تدعيم ما سبق وعلمته المدرسة.	1	2	3	4	5
20. Letting my child to read or to tell me at story in English at home. أطلب من طفلي أن يقرأ أو يخبرني قصة باللغة الانكليزية في البيت.	1	2	3	4	5

PART IV – Parental Willingness to Participate in Child’s Educational Program

رغبة الأباء بالمشاركة في برنامج طفلهم التربوي

Directions: Some teachers assume all parents are willing to support their child’s educational program both at home and at preschool. How willing are you to participate in the following activities? Circle the number of your answer.

توجيهات: يفترض بعض المعلمين أن جميع الأهل يرغبون في دعم برنامج طفلهم التربوي في المنزل و في المدرسة. ما مدى رغبتك بالمشاركة في الأنشطة التالية؟ ضع دائرة حول الرقم الذي يمثل جوابك.

Definitely not Willing: DNW بالتأكيد غير راغب
Probably not Willing: PNW ربما غير راغب
Probably Willing: PW محتمل الا اكون ربما راغباً
Willing: W راغب
Very Willing: VW راغب جداً

Activities	DNW	PNW	PW	W	VW
1. Attend workshops to help me understand my child’s individual style of learning. أحضر ورش عمل لمساعدتي على فهم أسلوب طفلي في التعلم.	1	2	3	4	5
2. Provide a quiet place for my child to rest, think, and work alone. أوفر مكان هادئ لطفلي للراحة، والتفكير، والعمل على انفراد.	1	2	3	4	5
3. Let my child participate in community and preschool programs that offer rewards such as certificates or books. أسمح لطفلي بالمشاركة في البرامج الاجتماعية ومرحلة الحضانه التي تقدم المكافآت مثل الشهادات أو الكتب.	1	2	3	4	5
4. Control the amount of time my child spends watching TV and the types of programs. أتحكم بوقت مشاهدة طفلي للتلفاز وبأنواع البرامج.	1	2	3	4	5
5. Reading aloud to my child every day. أقرأ لطفلي بصوت مرتفع يومياً.	1	2	3	4	5
6. Arranging workshops with my child’s teacher about reading or speaking in English.	1	2	3	4	5

أنظم ورش عمل مع معلّمة طفلي عن القراءة أو التكلم باللغة الانكليزية.					
Activities	DNW	PNW	PW	W	VW
7. Help my child at home with assignments or any kind of educational activities. أساعد طفلي في اتمام فروضه أو أي نوع من النشاطات المدرسية.	1	2	3	4	5
8. Working in the preschool as an aide, parent tutor, parent volunteer, teacher, or other such jobs. أعمل في الحضانة كمساعد، معلّم خاص، متطوّع، مدرس، أو القيام بأية أعمال أخرى.	1	2	3	4	5
9. Broaden my child's background of experiences, (take child on field trips, vacations, public library or bookmobile). أوسع خلفية طفلي الخبراتية، (اصطحاب طفلي في رحلات ميدانية، اجازات، المكتبات العامة أو المكتبة المتجولة).	1	2	3	4	5
10. Buy books and other educational materials for my child to use at home. أشتري كتب أو مواد تربوية اخرى لطفلي ليستخدمها في المنزل.	1	2	3	4	5
11. Find out about my child's speaking English progress. اتعرّف على مدى تقدم طفلي في التحدث باللغة الانكليزية	1	2	3	4	5
12. Attend parent workshops at preschool. أحضر ورش العمل الخاصة بالاهل التي تنظمها الحضانة.	1	2	3	4	5
13. Take university courses or attending seminars to prepare myself to help my child with reading or speaking assignments. أتسجل في بعض المقررات الجامعية أو حضور ندوات لإعداد نفسي على مساعدة طفلي في القراءة أو الفروض الشفوية.	1	2	3	4	5
14. Set standards for speech in the home that will enable my child to communicate easily outside the home. أضع معايير للتخاطب في المنزل والتي تمكن طفلي من التواصل بسهولة خارج المنزل.	1	2	3	4	5
15. Providing books and magazines for my child to read in English. أؤمّن كتب ومجلات ليقرأها لطفلي طفلي باللغة الانكليزية	1	2	3	4	5
16. Subscribe to children's periodicals. أشترك في مجلة دورية للاطفال.	1	2	3	4	5
17. Use reference books; for example, dictionaries, encyclopedias, almanacs, and so on. أستخدم الكتب المرجعية؛ على سبيل المثال، القواميس والموسوعات، التقاويم، الخ...	1	2	3	4	5
18. Provide outside tutorial assistance for my child if necessary. أقدم مساعدة تعليمية خارجية لطفلي إذا لزم الأمر.	1	2	3	4	5
19. Work to reinforce what the teacher has taught. أعمل على تعزيز ما درّسته المعلمة.	1	2	3	4	5
20. Let my child read to me at home or telling me a story in English. أطلب من طفلي أن يقرأ لي أو يخبرني في المنزل قصة باللغة الانكليزية.	1	2	3	4	5

APPENDIX B

RUBRIC

Checklist—Check the box if the child can perform the task				
Rating Scale—Indicate a number from 1 to 5				
1	2	3	4	5
cannot demonstrate the skill لا يستطيع اظهار المهارة	demonstrates few elements of the skill يظهر القليل من المهارة	demonstrates some elements of the skill يظهر بعض عناصر المهارة	demonstrates most elements of the skill يظهر معظم عناصر المهارة	demonstrates mastery of the skill يظهر ويتقن المهارة

	Rating معدل	Frequency
	1-5	<i>always, sometimes, never</i> دائماً، أحياناً، أبداً
Attitude سلوك		
Enthusiastic learner who seems to enjoy preschool. تلميذ متحمس ومستمتع في الحضانة..		
Appears well rested and ready for each day's activities. يظهر ارتياحاً وجهوية للقيام بالنشاطات اليومية.		
Shows enthusiasm for classroom activities يظهر حماسة للقيام بالنشاطات في الصف.		
Behavior تصرف		
Cooperates consistently with the teacher and other students. يتعاون باستمرار مع المعلمة والتلاميذ.		
Transitions easily between classroom activities without distraction. ينتقل بسهولة من نشاط صفي الى آخر دون انزعاج.		
Remains focused on the activity at hand. يحافظ على التركيز على النشاط الذي يقوم به.		
Character شخصية		
Treats preschool property and the belongings of others with care and respect. يحترم أغراض الحضانة وأغراض الآخرين ويحافظ عليها.		
Can be depended on to do what he/she is asked to do. يمكن الاعتماد عليه للقيام بما يطلب منه..		
Thoughtful in interactions with others. يتفاعل مع الآخرين.		
Interests and talents اهتمامات ومواهب		
Has a well-developed sense of humor. لديه حسن الفكاهة.		
Is a gifted performer.. موهوب في أدائه..		
Participation مشاركة		
Listens attentively to the responses of others. يستمع بامعان الى ردود الآخرين.		
Remains an active learner throughout the preschool day. يحافظ على نشاطه طوال اليوم الدراسي..		

CURRICULUM VITAE

Mireille Jean Feghaly

Personal Information

Date of Birth: September 8, 1982

Place of Birth: Wadi Chahrour Village, Beirut, Lebanon

Age: 35 years old

Civil Status: Married

Citizenship: Lebanese

Religion: Baptist

Mother's Name: Mona Bitar

Father's Name: Jean George Feghaly

Sisters' Names: Grace and Danielle

Brother's Name: George Feghaly

Educational Background

2000-2004 BA, Pedagogy, French Language cycle 2, Lebanese University, Beirut

Work Experience

Current Assignment Preschool Director, Grow Early Learning Center, Philemon Project.

2005 – 2016 Class Teacher, Kids Alive School, Dar el Awlad

2002 – 2004 French Teacher, Lycée National Libanais, Haddath